

SMART ERA

Smartness Assessment methodology/D2.1

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Glossary

DASHBOARD: A dashboard is a tool used to consolidate and display data visually, providing at-a-glance insights into key aspects of a specific objective or process. It typically organizes diverse but interrelated information in a single interface, designed to be easily digestible and actionable.

ICT: Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) is a broader term for Information Technology (IT), which refers to all communication technologies, including the internet, wireless networks, cell phones, computers, software, middleware, video-conferencing, social networking, and other media applications and services enabling users to access, retrieve, store, transmit, and manipulate information in a digital form.¹

IMPACT INDICATORS: Impact indicators focus on long-term outcomes, tracking measurable progress toward overarching objectives of smartness. They provide evidence of change resulting from programs and strategies, highlighting their broader societal, environmental, and economic effects.

INDICATOR: a pointer, sign, instrument, tool, which quantifies the value of a variable.

ISO: the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) is an independent, non-governmental international organization. It brings global experts together to agree on standardised, and possibly optimal, ways to measure status or achieve change. According to their mission, from climate change and healthcare, to quality management and artificial intelligence, ISO aims to make lives easier, safer and better – for everyone, everywhere²

KPIs: Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are critical, quantifiable measures of progress toward intended results (represented by Result Indicators). They help focus attention on operational priorities, provide an analytical foundation for decision-making, and emphasize what matters most. Effective project management with KPIs involves setting clear targets (desired performance levels) and monitoring progress against these targets over time. This approach ensures continuous improvement, strategic alignment, and accountability throughout the project lifecycle.

LIKERT SCALE: Developed in 1932 by Rensis Likert to measure attitudes, the typical Likert scale is a 5- or 7-point ordinal scale used by respondents to rate the degree to which they agree or disagree with a statement.³

¹Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) | AIMS. (s.d.). Obtained in December 16, 2024, from <https://aims.fao.org/information-and-communication-technologies-ict>

²ISO - International Organization for Standardization. (December 6, 2024). ISO. <https://www.iso.org/home.html>

³Joshi, A., Kale, S., Chandel, S., & Pal, D. K. (2015). Likert Scale: Explored and Explained. *Current Journal of Applied Science and Technology*, 396–403. <https://doi.org/10.9734/BJAST/2015/14975>

Sullivan, G. M., & Artino, A. R. (2013). Analyzing and Interpreting Data From Likert-Type Scales. *Journal of Graduate Medical Education*, 5(4), 541–542. <https://doi.org/10.4300/JGME-5-4-18>

METRICS: Metrics are measures of quantitative assessment commonly used for assessing, comparing, and tracking performance or production.

RESULT INDICATORS: They reflect the benefits to end users resulting directly from project implementation. These indicators are vital for adaptive, community-driven development, serving as a basis for evaluating a project's effectiveness, relevance, sustainability, and impact at local level. By measuring expected outcomes, Result Indicators reveal changes attributable to the project locally. To ensure clarity and maintain focus, projects should concentrate on a limited number of Result Indicators, ideally no more than 10.

SDGs: The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are a collection of 17 global objectives established by the United Nations in 2015 as part of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development

SESAM: It is the Smart ERA Smartness Assessment Method, the main deliverable of Task 2.1 of the project.

SMART VILLAGE: Although there is no official definition of a 'smart village' within EU legislation, there are a number of definitions and distinguishing features associated with the smart village concept, with the involvement of the local community and the use of digital tools being seen as core elements. The concept implies the participation of local people in improving their economic, social or environmental conditions, cooperation with other communities, social innovation and the development of smart village strategies⁴.

⁴Ana Martinez Juan & James McEldowney. (2021). Smart villages. Concept, issues and prospects for EU rural areas (PE 689.349; p. 12). EPRS | European Parliamentary Research Service. [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/689349/EPRS_BRI\(2021\)689349_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2021/689349/EPRS_BRI(2021)689349_EN.pdf)

1. Introduction

This Report presents **SESAM**, the **Smart ERA Smartness Assessment Method**, the main deliverable of the project's Task 2.1.

The Report includes a brief **introduction** to the context of smart villages and smartness assessment, an overview of the **road taken** within Smart ERA for the creation of SESAM, including the Literature Review on Smartness Assessment Methods, the detailed presentation of **SESAM**, a brief outline of its relationship with the **ISO 37122** standard for Smart Cities and Communities, and some reflections on the relationship of SESAM with both Smart ERA's Smart Innovation Packages (**SIP**, being developed within WP3), the project's **data dashboard** included in WP4 and Smart ERA's other WPs. The report concludes with a summary of findings and insights, offering direction for future developments both within the project and beyond.

The Report also includes, as **annexes**, the comprehensive tools designed to assess smartness from both **qualitative** and **quantitative** perspectives: **Annex 1** presents the qualitative survey, **Annex 2** details the emotional mapping approach, and **Annex 3** outlines quantitative indicators along with their associated metrics.

2. The what and why of a smartness assessment method for rural areas

In 2019, Visvizi and co-workers⁵, in their “Smart Villages in the EU and beyond”, asked themselves what would make a village “smart”: “*Is it life, water, energy, community or food? Is it technology, the ways and means, or the status? What do villages, or rural areas in the concept, actually stand for?*”

Smartness assessment methods aim to create a rationale to answer that very question in all its aspects, and also to help rural communities, by extension villages, to assess their status and to set priorities for further development.

In planning and development analyses, the term **assessment** for rural areas may in fact refer to any type of evaluation or analysis, either qualitative or quantitative or a mixture of the two, of how well a rural community or area is able to integrate IT technology, infrastructure, and digital services to improve the quality of life for its residents, support sustainable development, foster economic growth, guarantee attractiveness and counter depopulation.

Assessing the “smartness” of a rural area, often referred to as its level of “smartness”, “smart development”, or “readiness with respect to digital transition”, is important because it helps identify how well the community is utilising technology, innovation, and more extensively sustainable practices to improve the quality of life for its residents. More broadly, the concept includes the idea of bridging the divide between the attractiveness, the social vitality and the economic performance of urban areas and those of rural areas, that more often than not lag behind, mostly by the use of ICT tools and technologies⁶.

Placing itself in the EU-wide context of smarter and more sustainable rural areas, and building on the outcomes and results of several EU-co funded projects, strategies and plans, the overall aim of task 2.1 within Smart ERA, with its creation of a customised smartness assessment method, is to work in the context of acknowledging and countering the so-called “**Circle of Decline**” of rural and mountain areas, as it is defined and recognized by the European Union, with a specific focus on the rural areas in the project.

Among the several EU co-funded projects that have contributed in creating the knowledge base on which the present activities within Smart ERA build, it is important to recall Interreg Alpine Space **INTESI** (Integrated territorial strategies for Services of General Interest, 2015-2018)⁷, Interreg Alpine Space **SmartVillages** (Smart digital transformation of villages in the Alpine Space, 2018-2021)⁸, Interreg Europe **P-IRIS** (Policies to improve rural areas' innovation systems by professionalising networking activities and use of innovation tools,

⁵ Visvizi, M. D. Lytras, and G. Mudri, *Smart Villages in the EU and Beyond*. Bingley, UK: Emerald Publishing Limited, 2019.

⁶ See, for example, the extensive 2022 work on this by V. I. Lakshmann and colleagues, in their “Smart Villages - Bridging the Global Urban-Rural Divide”, edited by Springer, ISBN: 978-3-030-68460-0.

⁷ <https://www.alpine-space.eu/project/intesi/>

⁸ <https://www.alpine-space.eu/project/smartvillages/>

2017-2021)⁹, and the ongoing projects Interreg Alpine Space **SmartCommUnity** (Building on the concept of Smart Villages towards a transnational and EUSALP-integrated Smart Community in the Alps, 2022-2025)¹⁰, Interreg Central Europe **More than a Village** (Smart village transition, a model for more competitive and attractive villages in Central Europe, 2023-2026)¹¹ and Interreg Europe **INSPIRE** (Innovative and Smarter Policy Instruments for Rural Europe, 2024-2028)¹².

The present work builds on the main findings of the aforementioned projects and is constructed via the main results, outcomes and experiences coming from the first year of project Smart ERA, with specific reference to WP2 and the project-wide activity of Literature Review on Smartness Assessment Methods, that will be more widely described in the following chapter.

As already defined within the INTESI project, in its work on the provision of services of general interest to mountain areas, the Circle of Decline of rural and mountain areas can be defined as including out-migration, mostly of the younger generations (with a corresponding ageing of the remaining population); a subsequent low population density; the lack of a critical mass of people for services and infrastructure; lower rate of business creation and innovation; fewer jobs. The latter rekindles the Circle of Decline itself, creating even fewer opportunities for local people and further diminishing the overall attractiveness of rural areas. The Circle of Decline rationale identifies two main interconnected reinforcing trends: a shortage of jobs and sustainable business opportunities and inadequate and declining basic services to the population, affecting the vitality and attractiveness of rural areas. Some of these aspects, mostly those related to the lack of jobs and attractiveness of rural areas, as well as the resulting lack of opportunities and the bleak economic outlook, have emerged as such within the first year of SMART ERA.

Over the last decade or so, the European Union in particular has increasingly focused on how to improve the conditions of rural (including mountain) areas in several dedicated documents. The Cork 2.0 declaration “A better life in rural areas” (2016) focused on strengthening emerging business opportunities, on new approaches to integration and on self-sustaining initiatives for a competitive and diversified economy. The subsequent **EU Action for Smart Villages** (2017)¹³ highlighted the need to enable new business models, to assist existing businesses to emerge, to integrate services and to cooperate better with urban-based businesses. On the same track, the **Bled Declaration** (2018)¹⁴ identified some technological achievements to inspire innovation in SGI provision in mountain areas, among which digital platforms offering all essential services, such as e-learning, e-health, e-administration, transport, social services. A strong focus of both initiatives, in this sense, is on the digitisation of rural areas, both in terms of providing equal digital infrastructure to non-urban areas, and in terms of increasing the digital literacy of rural and mountain areas.

⁹ <https://projects2014-2020.interregeurope.eu/p-iris/>

¹⁰ <https://www.alpine-space.eu/project/smartcommunity/>

¹¹ <https://www.interreg-central.eu/projects/more-than-a-village/>

¹² <https://www.interregeurope.eu/inspire>

¹³ https://ec.europa.eu/enrd/smart-and-competitive-rural-areas/smart-villages_en.html

¹⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/enrd/news-events/news/new-declaration-smarter-rural-areas_en.html

In more recent years, in this sense the number of EU initiatives, plans and strategies dedicated to enable rural and mountain areas to take full advantage of the opportunities belied by ICT and digital innovation has significantly expanded and increased. A dedicated **Smart Villages task force and working group** (2017-2020) was created within the European Network for Rural Development, that focused on the intersections between digital innovation and spatial planning in the context of agricultural development, on the gaps in digitisation both in terms of infrastructure, coverage and digital literacy and skills, which are of course key for rural and mountain areas, whereas in 2021 the EU has launched its **Long-term vision for rural areas**¹⁵, that includes a Rural Pact and a Rural Action Plan, and that focuses strongly on the emerging opportunities of the EU's green and digital transitions and on the lessons learnt from the COVID 19 pandemic for the rural areas of the continent. The Vision aims at rural areas that are stronger, connected, resilient and prosperous, with the 'connected' aim covering both physical and digital accessibility. In 2020, the **EU 2030 Territorial Agenda** also declared its scope of an action-oriented framework to promote territorial cohesion in Europe, a future for all places, including Action Plans for specific territories.

Even more recently, the EU discourse on smarter and more sustainable rural areas has seen the launch of the **Rural Toolkit** (2024)¹⁶, that focuses on policies at all levels to enable a smart transition for rural, including mountain, areas, the **Rural Observatory**, that aims at improving data collection and dissemination related to EU rural areas, offering relevant statistics, indicators and analyses based on data from multiple sources and at the most appropriate territorial granularity, covering the economic, social and environmental dimensions, and even a **European Startup Village Forum**, part of the EU Vision for rural areas, that facilitates the exchange of knowledge and expertise on how to promote start-up-driven innovation in rural areas.

In this captivating and ever evolving context, Smart ERA's Task 2.1 has aimed to provide a comprehensive and up-to-date smartness assessment method, SESAM, the development of which will be described from the following chapter.

¹⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_21_3162

¹⁶ <https://funding.rural-vision.europa.eu/>

3. The road to SESAM

The work behind the creation of SESAM has been wide-ranging and has started with the decision of completing a Literature Review of all most recent smartness assessment methods (SAMs) conceived for or applied in rural and mountain areas.

The Literature Review, detailed in a dedicated report, has been conducted in four different phases:

- Phase 1 - Designing the review - performed between April and May 2024
- Phase 2 - Conducting the review - performed between June and July 2024
- Phase 3 - Analysis – performed between July and August 2024
- Phase 4 – Finalisation of SESAM, as deliverable D2.1, performed between September to December 2024

The conclusions that were gathered from the Literature Review, and that have led to the construction of SESAM, are on two levels, one regarding the review itself and the main features of the SAMs collected by the SMART ERA partners, and another, more focused to the fulfilment of the preparation of deliverable D2.1. On the more general level, it has been observed that:

- **Range and topics:** The SAMs reviewed span a wide range of years and topics, providing a solid foundation for understanding the evolution and scope of SAM methodologies. A mixture of quantitative and qualitative methods prevails. More strictly ICT-related topics prevailed in the recent past, whereas more policy-related applications seem to prevail at present.
- **Methodological diversity:** The SAMs analysed have shown a variety of approaches, each with unique strengths and applicability scenarios, that have highlighted the importance of context-specific adaptation. A focus on specific contexts and research aims prevailed on wider context and more general analyses.
- **Applicability to SMART ERA, general consideration:** Most of the SAMs collected in the present Literature Review have shown potential for application in the project pilots, with specific indicators identified for optimal performance. Applicability varies according to the SAMs themselves, and to the specific features of SMART ERA's pilot areas.

As a first, general conclusion, the Literature Review highlighted the need for a SMART ERA-specific and tailored approach in developing SESAM, as a comprehensive smart assessment method that addresses the unique needs and challenges of the project's rural areas, as well as the need to select specific SAMs as ingredients of the Smartness Innovation Packages (SIPs) foreseen in WP3. More on this will be covered in the upcoming chapters.

More, in the more specific context towards the creation of SESAM, the following insights were gathered:

- **Insight 1:** specific territories may prefer, or need, or be in the position of assessing their own level of smartness, or more in detail of digital maturity, by means of only qualitative, descriptive, perceptive, or otherwise narrative approaches. The same approaches will be at the disposal of territories in the position of making use of more quantitative approaches, but such quantitative approaches are often, at least in the SAM sample we have gathered, nicely complemented by qualitative aspects. It was therefore decided for SESAM to include qualitative as well as quantitative sections.
- **Insight 2:** the concept of Smartness is most of the time subdivided in 'dimensions', or 'factors', or 'blocks', or 'aspects', or 'topics', or even 'questions', and this first-level division is almost invariably compounded by a second-level division into 'indicators'. Therefore, it was decided that SESAM include a differentiation into 'sectors of smartness', with further distinctions into a number of indicators and metrics. SESAM will be structured as an "ecosystem of dimensions", as per the definition given by Maja et al. 2020.
- **Insight 3:** Insight 3 resulting of the Literature Review has been the need to have SESAM include at the very least both the indicators of status and the indicators of result (including indicators of performance), i.e. to allow the rural areas that may decide to use SESAM both to assess the current situation and to set targets, and to monitor their progress towards such targets. As a matter of fact, moreover, specific SAMs could be included in the SIPs having a focus on the present situation, on the future, or a mixture of both. The structure of SESAM and its indicators and metrics, and its relationship with the SIPs, will be discussed in detail in the following chapters.
- **Insight 4:** Insight 4, for the creation of SESAM and the inclusion of SAMs as ingredients of the SIPs, can be summarised in the need for any SAM to allow for both immediately tangible actions, and for more long-term policy making, policy improvement and policy refinements at the relevant level. This also covers the relationship of SESAM with the project's data dashboard in WP4, and with the action of pilot areas in WPs 3-to-5, and will be discussed further.
- **Insight 5:** As a particularly ambitious insight, the ISO 37122 "Indicators for smart cities" standard, approved by ISO in 2019 in the context of the ISO 37120 "Indicators for city services and quality of life" is acknowledge as a possible target for smartness assessment standardisation also for rural areas. The ISO 37122 standard includes 12 dimensions with several indicators that allow for the assessment of the level of smartness of cities and, nominally, also 'communities'. One of the ambitions of SMART ERA could be the drafting of a similar, co-created and agreed, standard for rural communities and villages, and more on this will be discussed in a specific chapter in the following.

- **Insight 6:** Connecting the two levels of conclusions, it was decided that, in the construction of SESAM, it was necessary to include a wide range of digital transition activities in the SESAM itself. At the same time, it has been deemed fundamental to identify specific more narrow-focus SAMs as single ingredients of the SIPs.

These six Insights have represented the building blocks of the development of SESAM, which will be described in its entirety in the next chapter.

4. SESAM

SESAM is designed to offer a comprehensive **qualitative** and **quantitative analysis** of the factors that contribute to the **smart development** of a given territory, helping to assess the maturity of smartness in various dimensions and identifying strengths and potential gaps in each of them. SESAM is also conceived to inspire changes and monitor them, as well as to set priorities for future work.

4.1. SESAM dimensions

The SESAM model captures specific dimensions or areas related to the concept of smartness but having an emphasis on some specific quality differentiating it from the main concept. The **six general dimensions of smartness** identified are: **Enabling Factors, Mobility and Transport, Economy, Governance and Policies, Services of general interest, Environment and climate-related SDGs**. These dimensions were identified through a Literature Review on Smartness Assessment Methods and compiled in the Intermediate Report for D2.1 – Analysis and Insights for Task 2.1.

Each dimension contains different **sub-dimensions, or specific topics**, that serve as a headline for analysis. Sub-dimensions are a further refinement into related but specific areas of a specific dimension (see Table 1).

Table 1. SESAM dimensions and topics

Enabling Factors	Mobility and Transport	Economy	Governance and Policies	Services of general interest	Environment and climate-related SDGs
<i>Digital Infrastructure</i>	<i>Technical and Information Infrastructure</i>	<i>Primary sector</i>	<i>Public Governance</i>	<i>Healthcare</i>	<i>Protection, Conservation, and Enhancement of Natural Capital</i>
<i>Digital Literacy</i>	<i>Mobility Methods and Vehicles used for this purpose</i>	<i>Secondary Sector</i>	<i>Non-Governmental Support</i>	<i>Education</i>	<i>Mitigation of Environmental Pressures and Risks</i>
	<i>Legal</i>	<i>Tertiary and Advanced Tertiary Sector</i>	<i>Policy Development and Implementation</i>	<i>General Services</i>	<i>Development of a Resource-Efficient, Low-Carbon Economy</i>

4.1.1 Enabling Factors

Enabling factors are conditions or resources that facilitate or simplify the ability of individuals or communities to change their behavior or improve their environment. In the context of

digital transformation and technological access, enabling factors represent a critical dimension of SESAM, as they empower rural areas to effectively adopt and leverage digital technologies and services.

Research highlights the presence of a **hierarchy of factors** that are instrumental in driving smart revitalization, both in urban and rural contexts. For example, concepts often associated with "smart cities" include factors such as **technology**, **social infrastructure**, **governance**, **triple-helix partnerships** (collaborations between academia, industry, and government), and **information services**, as emphasized in a case study presented at the Thirty-Seventh International Conference on Information Systems (2016).¹⁷

Similarly, rural revitalization frameworks align with this perspective while addressing the specific needs of rural areas. For instance, the European Network for Rural Development (ENRD) Thematic Group in 2021 identified **policy design (structures)** and **local empowerment (people)** as essential building blocks for sustainable rural development¹⁸. These enabling factors, while tailored to rural contexts, complement and reinforce the broader principles of digital transformation seen in smart city initiatives.

From the perspective of SESAM and its Smart Assessment Methods (SAMs), the literature reviews identify two key sub-dimensions of enabling factors:

- **Digital Infrastructure:** Refers to the physical and software systems, such as broadband connectivity, data networks, and cloud services, that support digital interactions and services.
- **Digital Literacy:** Represents the skills and knowledge required to effectively and critically use digital technologies, ensuring inclusivity and competence in the evolving digital landscape.

Together, these enabling factors provide the foundation for meaningful and equitable digital participation.

Digital Infrastructure

Digital infrastructure refers to the physical and virtual systems that support digital services and technologies. This includes the hardware, software, networks, and data centres that organizations rely on to operate and communicate. Digital infrastructure also encompasses more advanced elements such as cloud computing and cybersecurity systems, which ensure secure and scalable access to digital resources. Equitable access is a crucial aspect of digital infrastructure, ensuring that all individuals and organizations can leverage these technologies effectively. In alignment with the European Parliament and Council's 2006 Recommendation¹⁹, digital infrastructure requires not just physical resources but also specific competencies to make profitable use of these technologies. This means that

¹⁷ Petercsak, R., Maccani, G., Donellan, B., Helfert, M., & Connolly, N. (2016). Enabling Factors for Smart Cities: A Case Study. 37th International Conference on Information Systems (ICIS 2016), 3, 1628–1637.

¹⁸ Gómez, G. H. (2022). Enabling factors for rural revitalisation & a self-assessment tool for policy design (Thematic Group Report, p. 18) [ENRD Thematic Group on Rural Revitalisation]. European Network for Rural Development. https://enrd.ec.europa.eu/publications/enabling-factors-rural-revitalisation-self-assessment-tool-policy-design_en

¹⁹ Document 32006H0962: Recommendation of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 December 2006 on key competences for lifelong learning OJ L 394, 30.12.2006, p. 10–18. ELI: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reco/2006/962/oj>

effective use of digital infrastructure demands skills and knowledge to manage and navigate these systems properly.

Digital Literacy

Digital literacy goes beyond basic computer skills to encompass the ability to use digital technologies confidently, critically, and effectively in everyday life. It includes competencies such as retrieving, evaluating, storing, producing, presenting, and exchanging information through various technologies. Digital literacy also includes the ability to communicate, collaborate, and participate in digital networks. The increasing integration of technology in both professional and personal contexts means that digital literacy is now fundamental for engagement in society, work, and leisure activities. It's a set of skills that enables individuals to interact with information society technologies (IST) to the full extent, empowering them to critically assess, use, and contribute to digital environments.

4.1.2 Mobility and Transport

Mobility and transport is recognized as a distinct and critical dimension, even though it could be considered part of services of general interest, due to its essential role in rural areas. While **transportation** refers to the **physical movement of goods or people** between locations, **mobility** highlights the **ability** of individuals to **move freely, efficiently, and sustainably**. It involves not only access to transportation options but also ensuring their quality, inclusivity, and efficiency for all users.

The European Union (EU) is leading the transition toward a sustainable, intelligent, and inclusive mobility system, striving to create a friendly transport network that serves citizens across both urban and rural areas. This transformation is driven by digitalization and innovative solutions, such as on-demand bus services, vehicle-sharing programs, and optimized public transport routes.

In rural areas, unique challenges such as lower population density, longer travel distances, and infrequent transportation options demand targeted approaches. These challenges present opportunities to deploy innovative technologies and policies that enhance mobility. For instance, real-time tracking systems for buses, shared mobility services adapted to local needs, and integrated infrastructure planning can make rural transportation systems more accessible, cost-effective, and environmentally sustainable. To comprehensively address mobility in rural areas, it is essential to consider also the following sub-dimensions as identified by Orlowski and Romanowska (2019)²⁰:

Technical and Information Infrastructure

This sub-dimension focuses on the physical and digital infrastructure that supports mobility, such as road networks, bike paths, charging stations for electric vehicles, and digital tools like apps for real-time transport tracking. In rural areas, improving infrastructure can include implementing digital platforms to coordinate transportation schedules or establishing robust broadband connectivity to support smart mobility solutions.

²⁰ Orlowski & Romanowska (2019) Smart Cities Concept: Smart Mobility Indicator. Cybernetics and Systems, 50:2, 118-131, DOI: 10.1080/01969722.2019.1565120

Mobility Methods and Vehicles used for this purpose

This sub-dimension refers to the variety of transportation modes available, such as public buses, bicycles, electric scooters, and carpooling. In rural regions, innovative mobility methods like on-demand mini-buses or community-driven ride-sharing programs can address challenges related to low population density and scattered settlements.

Legislation

Policies and regulations play a pivotal role in fostering smart mobility. This includes laws promoting sustainable transport modes, incentives, and plans to adapt mobility models to rural settings.

4.1.3 Economy

The Economy dimension within SESAM encompasses both **agricultural** and **non-agricultural industries** that are pivotal in shaping the livelihood, resilience, and sustainability of rural communities. This dimension assesses the economic climate and the attractiveness of rural areas for businesses, investors, start-ups, and workers.

Unlike urban economies, rural areas rely on distinct characteristics such as agricultural activities, small-scale industries, and natural resources. However, they face persistent challenges, including:

- Low productivity
- Underinvestment in agriculture and non-farm rural employment
- Inadequate infrastructure
- Unsafe working conditions
- Limited or no access to essential services, including financial services

Addressing these challenges necessitates tailored strategies that reflect the unique dynamics of rural economies while promoting growth and long-term sustainability.

Rooted in the unique characteristics and resources of rural areas, this dimension is divided into three **sub-dimensions** related to **sectoral activities**. Dividing the economy into sectors allows researchers and stakeholders to analyze economic activity within categories of businesses that share similar or related functions, products, or services. These sub-dimensions provide a framework to identify smart indicators tailored to rural economic contexts.

Primary Sector

The primary sector is the foundation of rural economies, focusing on the extraction and harvesting of natural resources. Key activities include agriculture, livestock farming, forestry, fishing, aquaculture, mining, and quarrying. These industries provide essential goods, employment, and cultural heritage, forming the backbone of rural livelihoods. Modernizing and ensuring the sustainability of this sector is critical to achieving food security, preserving ecosystems, and maintaining economic stability.

Secondary Sector

In rural contexts, the secondary sector often centres on energy production. Increasing emphasis on sustainability highlights the importance of renewable energy, decentralized systems, and energy efficiency. Smart energy initiatives strengthen the autonomy of rural communities, reduce environmental impacts, and contribute to broader climate objectives, making this sector a key component of economic resilience and diversification.

Tertiary and Advanced Tertiary Sector

The tertiary sector encompasses services vital to rural economies, such as tourism and business-related activities. Tourism leverages the cultural and natural assets of rural areas, boosting local incomes and diversifying economic opportunities. Advanced tertiary services, including finance, banking, and digital platforms, foster innovation and enhance access to markets, opening pathways for collaboration and growth. These services play a critical role in improving the quality of life and driving economic vitality in rural communities.

4.1.4 Smart Governance and Policy

The Governance and Policy dimension explores how effective governance and policy play in **enabling rural communities** to embrace innovation, enhance digital capacity, and address societal challenges. Governance in this context refers to the **political and institutional frameworks** established by public and non-public entities, as well as the collaborative dynamics between stakeholders. It also encompasses the mechanisms through which policies are formulated, implemented, and monitored to ensure progress in digital transformation and broader rural development.

The following sub-dimensions form the basis of smart governance and policy assessment.

Public Governance

This dimension evaluates the involvement and support of public entities in driving rural development and digitalization efforts. It measures the commitment, resources, and leadership provided by government actors at various levels to foster innovation and growth in rural areas.

Non-Governmental Support

The role of non-public organizations, including civil society organizations (CSOs), research institutions, and private entities, is critical in complementing public governance efforts. This dimension assesses how these actors contribute to digital initiatives and rural development, highlighting the importance of multi-sector collaboration.

Policy Development and Implementation

This dimension examines the processes involved in creating, adapting, and executing policies that facilitate digital transformation. It considers how these policies address critical societal issues such as privacy, security, and equitable access to digital resources.

Additionally, it evaluates the effectiveness of inter-sectoral coordination and institutional capacities to implement policies and monitor their outcomes.

4.1.5 Services of General Interest

This dimension focuses on the **quality of life** for rural residents and visitors across all age groups and demographics. By prioritizing individual well-being and fostering sustainable, thriving communities, services of general interest play a central role in rural development.

Rural areas, however, face unique challenges in delivering these services, including:

- Shrinking budgets
- Depopulation
- Aging populations

Smart approaches to services of general interest aim to address these challenges by improving **accessibility, inclusivity, and reliability**. Leveraging innovative technologies, such as digital platforms, Internet of Things (IoT) solutions, and data-driven tools can streamline and enhance service delivery. Furthermore, fostering civic and social engagement ensures that services remain aligned with the evolving needs of rural communities, creating a foundation for long-term sustainability and resilience.

This dimension of the SESAM framework is structured around three interconnected sub-dimensions that are critical to supporting rural communities:

Healthcare

Healthcare services are essential for ensuring the health and safety of rural populations and are recognized as a fundamental human right. Access to quality healthcare includes hospitals, clinics, vaccination programs, and healthcare personnel (e.g., doctors, nurses, pharmacists). Innovative solutions such as eHealth and Ambient Assisted Living (AAL) technologies are particularly valuable in rural settings, enabling remote care, chronic condition management, and support for elderly residents. These approaches improve not only healthcare access but also the overall quality of care and safety for all.

Education

Education is a cornerstone of rural development, playing a key role in transmitting knowledge, skills, and cultural values across generations. It involves both physical infrastructure (e.g., schools, classrooms, laboratories) and organizational frameworks (e.g., curricula, student assessments, administrative processes). Digital inclusion is increasingly important, with e-learning platforms and connected classrooms helping to overcome the geographic and logistical challenges often faced in rural education systems.

General Services

General services encompass essential public functions that support daily life in rural communities, including postal services, banking, and local government services. These services are foundational to maintaining quality of life, enabling economic activity, and

fostering social cohesion. Smart solutions—such as digital platforms and IoT-enabled systems—can improve accessibility, efficiency, and sustainability, making these services more user-friendly and impactful.

4.1.6 Environment and Environmental and Climate-Related SDGs

This dimension focuses on the essential theme of environmental sustainability, aligned with the **"planet" cluster** of the **2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development**. As emphasized by the European Environmental Agency²¹, this cluster underscores the urgent need to protect our planet from degradation through sustainable consumption and production, responsible management of natural resources, and proactive climate action. In rural areas, environmental challenges often have compounded effects, impacting not only local communities but also local ecosystems and rural economies, threatening long-term viability and resilience.

However, through the lens of the SESAM framework, environmental sustainability is not merely a goal but a fundamental principle for rural development. By integrating smart practices and leveraging advanced technologies, rural communities can effectively address environmental challenges while actively contributing to global sustainability targets. The smart use of digital tools, data-driven solutions, and innovative methods can transform how rural areas conserve natural resources, mitigate environmental risks, move towards sustainable, green economies, and also lead the way in achieving climate resilience.

To work on these priorities, this dimension is structured around three interconnected sub-dimensions:

Protection, Conservation, and Enhancement of Natural Capital

This sub-dimension focuses on efforts to preserve biodiversity, sustain ecosystems, and improve the resilience of natural resources in rural areas. Strategies target the protection of wildlife habitats, the prevention of land degradation, and the preservation of vital ecosystems that provide essential services. Through these actions, rural areas aim to secure a healthy and thriving environment, one that supports both current and future generations while maintaining ecological balance.

Mitigation of Environmental Pressures and Risks

Rural regions often face heightened environmental pressures such as pollution, land mismanagement, and the pervasive impacts of climate change. This sub-dimension explores strategies to reduce these hazards, with a particular focus on pollution control, sustainable land use, and safeguarding water and air quality. Smart approaches, including the use of remote sensing, IoT sensors, and digital monitoring systems, play a key role in identifying risks and implementing effective mitigation strategies. These efforts are vital for building climate-resilient communities, reducing environmental health risks, and enhancing the well-being of rural residents.

²¹ European Environment Agency. (2020). Sustainable development goals and the environment in Europe: A cross country analysis and 39 country profiles. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2800/044724>

Development of a Resource-Efficient, Low-Carbon Economy

Transitioning to a low-carbon, resource-efficient economy is crucial for the future of rural areas. This sub-dimension emphasizes the adoption of green practices, including renewable energy solutions, energy-efficient technologies, and circular economy approaches. By embracing these sustainable practices, rural communities can reduce their carbon footprint, lower energy costs, and foster long-term economic resilience. The use of smart grids, solar power, wind energy, and digital tools for resource management can help rural areas unlock new opportunities for economic growth while mitigating environmental impact.

4.2. Qualitative path

The initial approach for **assessing smartness** in rural communities across the six smart dimensions begins with acknowledging that rural stakeholders may lack a detailed roadmap for implementing smart measures in their activities. Nevertheless, they possess a profound understanding of the challenges facing their communities and have clear priorities regarding where to focus their efforts to address these issues. Additionally, stakeholders often hold valuable insights into the potential applications of digitalization and ICT tools within their respective sectors, informed by their day-to-day experiences.

As a foundational step in the assessment process, we propose conducting a **qualitative survey** to gather these insights and perceptions comprehensively. This will be complemented by an **emotional mapping** exercise to explore how individuals and communities relate to their environments through collective emotional experiences in the six smartness dimensions. These tools aim to provide a nuanced understanding of the local context, facilitating more targeted and effective interventions.

Qualitative Survey

This survey is designed to assess the smartness of rural communities by exploring six key dimensions of village and community development. It primarily uses qualitative questions to collect focused, meaningful feedback, and is structured to be administered periodically, enabling researchers and community leaders to track shifts in participant sentiment and perceptions over time.

The survey is intended to be completed collectively by community members, encouraging group discussions to ensure a comprehensive and well-rounded perspective on the topics being addressed. Furthermore, It is self-administered, with a fixed structure that presents closed-ended questions in a standardized order for all participants. The survey utilizes a **Likert-Type scale**²², where respondents rate their opinions or perceptions along a five-level

²² Joshi, A., Kale, S., Chandel, S., & Pal, D. K. (2015). Likert Scale: Explored and Explained. *Current Journal of Applied Science and Technology*, 396–403. <https://doi.org/10.9734/BJAST/2015/14975>; Sullivan, G. M., & Artino, A. R. (2013). Analyzing and Interpreting Data From Likert-Type Scales. *Journal of Graduate Medical Education*, 5(4), 541–542. <https://doi.org/10.4300/JGME-5-4-18>

continuum, ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree." This scale is particularly effective in measuring attitudes, opinions, or perceptions about specific aspects of smartness.

In addition to close-ended questions, the survey includes provisions for **open-ended responses**, enabling participants to elaborate on the rationale behind their ratings. These qualitative inputs provide valuable insights into local experiences and perspectives, enriching the depth and contextual relevance of the collected data. Participants are encouraged to share their experiences and provide detailed explanations in the designated sections, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of community viewpoints.

Data-driven dashboards for transparent and accountable decision-making

To enhance the coherence and effectiveness of the SMART ERA framework, the qualitative survey has been seamlessly incorporated into the Data-Driven Dashboards under WP4, Task 4.2, led by the University of Maribor. These dashboards provide an integrated visualization of critical data, enabling users to gain actionable insights into trends and developments. Designed as intuitive, interactive tools, the dashboards empower users to make informed decisions and implement targeted actions, aligning with SMART ERA's goal of advancing rural smartness assessments.

Data dashboards²³ are visual displays that present the most important information needed to achieve specific goals on a single screen. Effective dashboards act as monitoring tools that are understood at a glance, leveraging visual perception to communicate dense data clearly and concisely. While they are typically used during the communication phase of evaluation, **analytical dashboards** can also play a role in the analysis phase.

Strategic, analytical, and operational dashboards developed into SMART ERA address distinct communication needs, making it versatile tools for driving insights and actions. It bridges qualitative insights and quantitative data collection. Within each dimension, the survey includes questions designed to identify potential indicators or metrics that participants deem valuable for monitoring progress in their communities. These responses are instrumental in shaping relevant smart indicators, ensuring the dashboards are enriched with context-specific and community-informed data.

Beyond their integration into the dashboards, the SESAM survey has been extensively developed as a standalone tool, enabling other interested parties to assess their communities qualitatively. Annex 1 provides the complete survey questionnaire, which supports a robust, user-centered methodology for evaluating rural smartness. This questionnaire will further contribute to SMART ERA's WP3 objectives, forming part of the co-design process for Smart Innovation Plans (SIPs) aimed at fostering rural innovation and sustaining community engagement.

²³ Smith, V. S. (2013). Data Dashboard as Evaluation and Research Communication Tool. *New Directions for Evaluation*, 2013(140), 21–45. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ev.20072>

Emotional Mapping

Emotional mapping, a method rooted in **psychology**²⁴, explores the relationship between emotions, space, and lived experiences, particularly in sensitive or therapeutic contexts. It serves as a dynamic tool to understand how individuals and communities connect to their environments through **shared emotions**.

In SESAM, Emotional mapping examines the relationship between **emotions** and the **six key dimensions** that define rural "smartness": Enabling Factors, Mobility and Transport, Economy, Governance and Policies, Services of general interest, Environment and climate-related SDGs.

Emotions, while often perceived as personal, are profoundly shaped by social interactions and environmental contexts. Mapping these emotions offers a unique lens through which to explore the lived experiences of rural communities, providing insights into how they perceive and interact with their surroundings. By identifying these interactions, researchers and policymakers can better understand how communities experience their environments and how these feelings influence perceptions, decisions, and aspirations.

The Role of Collective Emotions

Emotions are intricate and multifaceted. Paul Ekman²⁵ identified six basic emotions—happiness, sadness, disgust, fear, surprise, and anger—that form the foundation for understanding emotional responses.

Table 2. Basic emotions, their function and manifestation

Emotion	Function	Manifestation
Happiness	Reinforces behaviours that benefit well-being and strengthen social bonds.	Smiling, laughter, and increased energy.
Sadness	Signals a loss or need for support, fostering social connection and empathy.	Tearfulness, withdrawal, and low energy.
Disgust	Protects from harmful substances or situations, both physical and moral.	Wrinkling the nose, turning away, revulsion.
Fear	Alerts to danger and triggers survival mechanisms like fight, flight, or freeze.	Increased heart rate, wide eyes, and alertness.
Surprise	Draws attention to unexpected events and prompts quick adaptation.	Raised eyebrows, open mouth, sudden focus.
Anger	Motivates action to overcome obstacles or address perceived injustices.	Frowning, raised voice, and physical tension.

²⁴ Goldman, A., Gervis, M., & Griffiths, M. (2022). Emotion mapping: Exploring creative methods to understand the psychology of long-term injury. *Methodological Innovations*, 15(1), 16–28. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20597991221077924>

²⁵ See, for example, here: <https://www.paulekman.com/universal-emotions/>

These are further expanded to include emotions like pride, shame, excitement, and embarrassment, capturing a broader spectrum of human experience.

Collective emotions, which are shared among members of a community, are particularly significant. These emotions stem from deep-rooted relationships with family, friends, and cultural contexts, reflecting the community's shared values, struggles, and achievements. Understanding collective emotions is crucial for grasping how a community as a whole feels about its rural environment and its potential for development.

Mapping Emotions and Making Sense

Although emotions are intangible, linking them to physical locations provides valuable insights into the **community's emotional** and **spatial dynamics**. Key concepts such as "legibility" (how easily a space is understood by its residents) and "imageability" (how specific locations evoke vivid imagery or emotions) help structure the process. These ideas have been effectively applied in geography²⁶, planning²⁷, and community development²⁸, with a growing tradition in psychology and sociology²⁹, and are now being adapted to rural contexts. By tying these emotional responses to specific locations, emotional mapping identifies the physical and social hotspots of satisfaction, concern, or ambivalence within a community.

The true strength of emotional mapping lies not only in its ability to spatially visualize emotions but also in its deeply **participatory nature**. Through collective discussions, participants share observations, personal experiences, and reflections, creating a richer, more nuanced emotional map. These shared dialogues uncover patterns and trends, fostering a deeper process of sensemaking—a critical framework for understanding and navigating the complexities of rural life.

Sensemaking, a concept introduced by Karl Weick, refers to the process through which individuals and communities assign **meaning** to their **collective experiences**. It is particularly essential in complex environments like rural areas, where change can be very slow but unevenly distributed. In this context, sensemaking serves as a powerful tool to interpret how communities perceive their surroundings, adapt to challenges, and envision their futures.

Incorporating sensemaking into emotional mapping enhances its depth and impact. While emotional mapping visually represents where collective emotions are distributed across a rural area, sensemaking provides the necessary context to understand why these emotions

²⁶ Steger, A., Evans, E., & Wee, B. (2021). Emotional cartography as a window into children's well-being: Visualizing the felt geographies of place. *Emotion, Space and Society*, 39, 100772. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emospa.2021.100772>

²⁷ S. Iaconesi and O. Persico, "Visualising Emotional Landmarks in Cities," 2014 18th International Conference on Information Visualisation, Paris, France, 2014, pp. 408-413, doi: 10.1109/IV.2014.87

²⁸ Pánek, J., & Benediktsson, K. (2017). Emotional mapping and its participatory potential: Opinions about cycling conditions in Reykjavík, Iceland. *Cities*, 61, 65–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2016.11.005>

²⁹ McGrath, L., Mullarkey, S., & Reavey, P. (2019). Building visual worlds: using maps in qualitative psychological research on affect and emotion. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 17(1), 75–97. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14780887.2019.1577517>

exist and how they influence community dynamics. Together, they form a complementary framework for interpreting the emotional and spatial dimensions of rural life.

For example, emotional mapping can highlight areas of intense frustration, pride, or concern. Sensemaking dives deeper, revealing the root causes of these emotions and their broader implications:

- If frustration is mapped near a poorly maintained road, sensemaking might uncover its cascading effects, such as limited access to markets or healthcare, impacting livelihoods and well-being.
- Pride associated with a preserved forest might reflect shared values around environmental stewardship, sustainability, and cultural identity.

Building Community Understanding

By collectively interpreting the emotional landscape, participants begin to identify and align around shared priorities, challenges, and opportunities. For instance:

- Discussions around mapped emotions might reveal a community consensus on the urgent need for better public services, which could then inform smart policy advocacy.
- A shared sense of pride in a community initiative, such as renewable energy adoption, might inspire expanded efforts in sustainable practices, supported by ICT tools.

This dual framework ensures that emotional insights are not only captured but also translated into actionable strategies that reflect local needs and aspirations across the six dimensions of rural smartness.

Annex 2 presents the complete Emotional Mapping tool, developed to support a robust and user-centered methodology for assessing rural smartness. This tool will be part of the SMART ERA WP3 ingredients of the Co-design of SIPs for rural innovation and sustaining community participation.

4.3. Quantitative path

For each of the **SESAM six dimensions** this report explores numerous examples of quantitative **indicators for smartness** and **community development**, drawing on frameworks and standards from international organizations and national agencies. SESAM sources include:

- the Literature Review on Smartness Assessment Methods within the SMART-ERA project
- the ISO 37122 smart cities indicator standard (Santana et al., 2018)
- the ITU (International Telecommunication Union) indicators related to:
 - the use of information and communication technology in smart sustainable cities (4901)
 - the sustainability impacts of information and communication technology in smart sustainable cities (4902);
 - smart sustainable cities to assess the achievement of sustainable development goals (4903);
- scientific articles and reports corresponding to specific metrics.

A combination of indicators can therefore provide a measuring system to inform about past trends, current realities, and future direction in order to aid decision making.³⁰

While substantial progress has been made toward defining assessment dimensions for smartness, there is no single, universally accepted set of indicators and the selection of indicators must consider each specific policy context's definition of smartness and data availability.

Rather than prescribing a rigid indicator set, this report offers a **framework** to support identifying and building a core set of indicators essential to understanding **smartness** in a **European context**. This flexible approach ensures SESAM's adaptability across diverse rural and village settings, promoting sustainability and connectedness while maintaining their unique rural identity.

Indicator components

This section summarizes the **key elements** involved in proposing and evaluating smartness Indicators, broken down into their components.

An **indicator** (spanning Status, Result, Performance, and Impact) serves as an essential building block for understanding the dynamics of a local system under analysis. These measurements, when analysed collectively, provide a comprehensive picture of past and current trends, enabling community leaders to make informed decisions about future outcomes. At their core, indicators reflect the complex interplay of social, environmental, and economic factors influencing a region's or community's well-being.

In the context of SESAM, each indicator is carefully designed to assess progress across the six key dimensions of smartness: Enabling Factors, Mobility and Transport, Economy,

³⁰ Phillips, R. (2003). Community indicators. American Planning Association.

Governance and Policies, Services of General Interest, and Environment and Climate-Related SDGs. By offering actionable insights, these indicators guide efforts to enhance sustainability, resilience, and smart development at the community level.

To be measurable, each indicator relies on a variety of metrics. A **metric** is a specific data point measured to capture aspects of smartness of villages and communities. Each metric is expressed in specific units designed to provide clear, quantifiable insights. These units may be or can be normalized to ensure consistency in data collection and comparison across different regions. Typical units include percentages, counts (e.g., per 100,000, per km², per firm), and other normalized values.

The importance of each metric is determined by its **relevance** to the smartness dimensions. **Importance** is further defined by the metric's ability to highlight key trends, reveal gaps, or provide actionable insights within rural contexts.

Typology of indicators

Indicators identified for SESAM can be categorized into Status, Result, Performance, and Impact indicators. Aligned with SESAM's quantitative approach, the initial focus is on **Status Indicators**, which serve as the foundation for assessing smartness. These indicators measure current conditions, providing a dynamic snapshot of smartness development across specific dimensions.

To ensure their effectiveness, reliability, and practicality in evaluating the smartness of villages and communities. Status Indicators has been developed following the **RACER criteria**:

- **Relevant:** Clearly linked to project objectives
- **Accepted:** Endorsed by partners and stakeholders
- **Credible:** Understandable to non-experts
- **Easy to Monitor:** Practical for regular assessment
- **Robust against Manipulation:** Resistant to bias or data tampering

Given that SMART ERA pilot areas will follow unique pathways to enhance the smartness of their villages, we recommend that stakeholders define **Impact Indicators**, **Result Indicators** and **Performance Indicators** tailored to their local needs. These should build upon Status Indicators and fundamental metrics as a baseline. To ensure quality, participants are asked to develop Impact Indicators, Result and Key Performance Indicators that adhere to the **RACER criteria**.

Indicator Framework for SESAM Dimensions

The indicators contained in this section aim to serve as a robust framework for measuring the progress and success of smart initiatives within rural communities and villages. SESAM defines 39 main indicators, each with specific metrics, as outlined into [Annex 3](#).

Table 3. SESAM framework

Dimensions	Sub-dimensions	Indicators	Definitions
Enabling factors	Digital infrastructure	Level of Digital Connectivity	Measures the availability and quality of digital network connections within a rural community.
		Level of Analog Connectivity	Assesses traditional, non-digital means of connectivity (e.g., postal services, telephony) to gauge infrastructure inclusivity in areas with limited digital access.
		Computational Capacity Potential	Evaluates the available computing resources and potential for scaling digital capabilities within rural areas.
		Economic Accessibility of Internet Services	Examines the affordability and economic accessibility of internet services for rural residents, aiming to highlight potential barriers to digital engagement.
	digital literacy	Technical Proficiency of Rural Populations	Evaluates the ICT skill levels within rural communities, reflecting their capability to leverage digital tools effectively.
Mobility and Transport	Technical information infrastructure and	Accessibility and Availability of Public Transportation Services	This indicator measures the extent to which public transport services are available and accessible to rural populations, including frequency, coverage, and proximity of services. It reflects the inclusiveness and usability of the transport network in addressing mobility needs in sparsely populated areas.
		Level of Digitalization in Public Transport	Evaluate the extent to which digital

		Systems and Infrastructures	technologies are integrated into public transport systems and infrastructures. It assesses features such as the availability of real-time information, digital ticketing systems, automated scheduling, smart traffic management, and integration with digital platforms
Mobility methods and vehicles used for this purpose		Modal Shift Transport	This indicator measures changes in transportation patterns, specifically the shift from traditional, less sustainable modes (e.g., private car usage) to more sustainable alternatives such as public transport, shared mobility, cycling, or walking.
		Low-Carbon Fuel Vehicles	This indicator assesses the adoption and use of vehicles powered by low-carbon or renewable fuels, such as electric vehicles (EVs), plug-in hybrids, or vehicles running on biodiesel, in rural areas.
		Integration of Smart ICT Solutions in Vehicles	This indicator evaluates the adoption of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) solutions in vehicles to enhance functionality, connectivity, and user experience.
Legislation		Adoption of Mobility Regulations and Plans	This indicator evaluates the extent to which rural areas have implemented and enforced mobility regulations and plans that promote sustainable, safe, and efficient transport

			systems. It reflects the level of institutional commitment to enhancing mobility and transport in rural regions.
Economy	Primary Sector	Status of Precision Agriculture Technologies	Measures the adoption of precision tools that optimize resource use and improve yield.
		Level of Digitization and Automation in Agricultural Systems	Evaluates the integration of digital and automated processes in farm management.
		Presence of Circular Agricultural Practices	Assesses the implementation of sustainable practices, such as waste reduction and resource recycling.
		Level of Investment in Innovative Agriculture	Indicates the extent of financial resources directed toward modernizing agricultural methods.
	Secondary Sector	Level of Decentralization in Electricity Production	Measures the spread of localized energy generation facilities, enhancing local energy resilience.
		Adoption of Circular Energy Solutions	Evaluates practices like energy recycling and renewable energy usage to reduce waste.
		Level of Digitalization in the Energy Sector	Assesses the integration of digital tools in managing and optimizing energy resources.
		Energy Storage Capacity	Measures the storage capabilities for renewable energy, supporting energy availability and reliability.
	Tertiary Sector / Advanced Tertiary Sector:	Level of Technical ICT Skills in the Labor Force	Evaluates the prevalence of ICT skills within the local workforce, supporting digital economy initiatives.

		Accessibility of Cultural and Recreational Initiatives	This indicator measures the ease with which residents and visitors in rural communities can access cultural and recreational activities including events, facilities, and programs.
		Economic Investment in ICT Sectors	Indicates the level of financial commitment to ICT industries, driving innovation and employment in rural areas.
Governance and Policy	Public Governance	Existence of Strategies, Rules, and Regulations to Promote ICT Literacy	Assesses the presence of formal policies, strategies, and regulations aimed at improving ICT literacy among citizens to enable digital inclusion and smart governance practices.
		Level of Information and Data Availability and Accessibility	Measures the extent to which community members have access to accurate, relevant, and up-to-date information and data for decision-making and participation in governance.
		Level of Online Service Accessibility	Evaluates the availability and usability of online public services for citizens and businesses.
		Level of Investment in Smart Transition Initiatives	Tracks the financial resources allocated by governments to projects and programs that drive smart development in rural communities.
	Non-Governmental Support	Level of Information and Data Availability and Accessibility	Assesses how non-governmental actors (e.g., NGOs, private organizations) contribute to providing relevant data and resources to the community.
		Level of Civil Society and Involvement	Measures the degree to which civil society

		Engagement in Policy Processes	organizations and citizens participate in policy-making and implementation processes.
		Level of Investment in Smart Transition Initiatives	Evaluates financial contributions from non-governmental actors to projects advancing smart rural development.
	Policy Development and Implementation	Level of Civil Society Involvement and Engagement in Policy Processes	Tracks the participation of civil society in shaping and executing policies at the local level.
		Level of Intersectionality in Rural Governance Practices	Measures the extent to which governance practices integrate diverse demographic, social, and economic perspectives to ensure equity and inclusion.
Services of General Interest	Healthcare	Level of Digitalization of Healthcare Systems	Assesses the extent to which digital technologies are integrated into healthcare systems in rural communities to improve access, efficiency, and quality of care.
	Education	Level of Digitalization in Rural Schools	Evaluates the integration and usage of digital technologies in rural educational institutions to enhance learning outcomes and accessibility.
	General Services	Level of Digital Accessibility in Services of General Interest	Measures the availability and ease of use of digital tools for accessing general public services in rural areas, such as administrative processes and utilities.
Environment and Environmental and Climate-Related SDGs	Protection, Conservation, and Enhancement of Natural Capital	Degree of Digitalization in Monitoring Systems	Evaluates the integration of digital technologies in monitoring environmental systems, such as ecosystems, water, air quality, noise,

			waste, and wastewater, to enhance data collection, analysis, and management.
	Mitigation of Environmental Pressures and Risks	Degree of Integrated Water Resource Management Implementation	Measures the extent to which integrated approaches to water management, incorporating digital tools, are implemented to optimize usage, reduce risks, and preserve resources.
		Level of Risk Reduction Systems Implemented	Evaluates the deployment of systems to mitigate environmental risks (e.g., flooding, drought, pollution) using digital and smart technologies.
	Development of a Resource-Efficient, Low-Carbon Economy	Status of Smart Waste and Recycling Management	Assesses the deployment of smart technologies to optimize waste collection, sorting, and recycling, promoting resource efficiency and reducing environmental impact.
		Status of Smart Water Resource Management	Measures the implementation of digital technologies in water resource management to enhance efficiency, reduce losses, and support conservation.

Self-Assessment

To ensure that critical indicators and metrics essential for participants' success are emphasized and that no key priorities are overlooked, this Report proposes a structured approach to **prioritization**. Recognizing limited funding and time, this prioritization, similar to a pairwise comparison, should guide participants in **ranking** all proposed dimensions, sub-dimensions and indicators.

Additionally, at the end of each dimension, SESAM includes a "**veto**" question. This question prompts respondents to identify which indicator or metric is deemed indispensable, specifically, the element that must be included for any action within that dimension to be effective.

Pairwise matrix

Before proceeding with the ranking process, participants are encouraged to carefully consider the following questions:

- *What is the relative significance of each indicator in achieving the objectives of the selected project?*
- *How does each specific indicator contribute to the success and long-term sustainability of the project?*

Once these considerations are made, all indicators are listed in a **pairwise comparison** matrix. Each pair of indicators is compared to determine their relative importance, as shown in the example table with three (A, B, C) random indicators:

Table 4. Pairwise Comparison Matrix

Indicators	3	2	1	2	3	Indicators
A	x					B
B			x			C
C		x				A

A double scale from 1 to 3 is used to assign preference values to each pair.

- Value **1**: The two indicators are equally important.
- Value **2**: One indicator is moderately more important than the other.
- Value **3**: One indicator is significantly more important than the other.

To ensure that every indicator is paired with every other indicator without repetitions, the concept of combinations can be applied. For n indicators, the number of unique pairs can be calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Number of pairs} = n \cdot (n-1)/2$$

After completing all pairwise comparisons, participants calculate the **total score** for each indicator using “points” across the rows. An indicator being deemed moderately or significantly more important than the other receives respectively 2 or 3 points (zero points are in this case allocated to the ‘losing’ indicator), whereas two indicators deemed equally important receive 1 point each.

Based on the matrix above:

Indicator A vs Indicator B: 3 vs 0
 Indicator B vs Indicator C: 1 vs 1
 Indicator C vs Indicator A: 2 vs 0

In this case, both Indicators A and C score 3 points, whereas Indicator B scores 1. Further discussion, if needed, can help select between Indicators A and C, or both can be retained for further analysis. Indicator B gets discarded from the present evaluation.

Once all scores are calculated, participants rank the indicators by importance. The indicator, or the indicators group, with the highest score represents the most important or **prioritized indicator**.

This approach enables communities to allocate resources efficiently, focusing on areas that best address their specific needs and objectives within the SESAM framework.

Veto Factor

The use of additive models for aggregating criteria is common in many multicriteria decision methods due to their straightforward scoring approach. However, a significant drawback of this compensatory approach is its ability to overshadow very low performance in certain criteria with high performance in others. This is problematic when some conditions are non-negotiable for the success of a project. For instance, alternatives that fail to meet critical thresholds—referred to as Veto Factors—cannot be prioritized, regardless of their overall evaluation.

Veto Factors represent indicators or conditions that are indispensable and cannot be compromised. They serve as a veto mechanism, preventing alternatives from being selected if they perform inadequately in critical areas. Thus, a sort of additive-veto models³¹ can be introduced to address this issue, particularly in choice and ranking problems, ensuring that any alternative failing to meet these fundamental requirements is excluded or de-prioritized, despite its relative ranking or compensatory advantages in other areas.

Implementation of the Veto Factor in SESAM occurs in three steps:

- 1. Identification:**

After finalizing the ranking of indicators, stakeholders should reflect on the essential indicators that directly impact the project's core objectives and feasibility. Any indicator that directly influences the project's success or its ability to meet legal, technical, or environmental requirements should be considered as a Veto Factor.

- 2. Assessment:**

If any indicator is flagged as a Veto Factor, it must be treated with utmost importance in the decision-making process, even if its ranking in the pairwise comparison is lower than others. The Veto Factor can also help prioritize resources towards meeting these critical conditions.

- 3. Actionable Insights:**

When completing the ranking and prioritization of indicators, stakeholders should ensure that the Veto Factor is integrated into the final decision.

³¹ De Almeida, A. T. (2013). Additive-veto models for choice and ranking multicriteria decision problems. *Asia-Pacific Journal of Operational Research*, 30(06), 1350026. <https://doi.org/10.1142/S0217595913500267>

For example, in a SESAM Dimension Six project focused on improving the sub-dimension “mitigation of environmental pressures and risks,” a Veto Factor could be the presence of a “digital monitoring system infrastructure.” Without this critical framework, the project would lack the ability to track the performance of other key indicators. This necessity overrides other indicators, such as the “level of risk reduction systems implemented in rural communities,” even if those indicators are ranked higher in terms of participants' interest. The Veto Factor ensures that the foundational capabilities required for effective implementation and monitoring are in place.

5. ISO 37122 and SESAM - a more ambitious path

ISO standards are a set of internationally recognized guidelines or specifications developed and published by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO). These standards cover a wide range of topics, including technology, safety, quality, environmental management, and many other areas of business and manufacturing.

The main purposes of ISO standards are to ensure that products, services, and systems are safe, reliable, and of high quality, and to facilitate international trade by ensuring that goods and services meet consistent criteria.

As such, the key features of ISO standards can be summarised as follows:

International Consistency: ISO standards are developed through collaboration among experts from different countries to ensure a common framework for various industries.

Voluntary Adoption: Although ISO standards are not legally binding, they are widely adopted by organisations and governments to demonstrate compliance with best practices.

Continuous Improvement: ISO standards are regularly reviewed and updated to stay relevant with technological advances and changing market needs.

In this context, in 2018 the family of **ISO standards 37120 - “Sustainable cities and communities — Indicators for city services and quality of life”³²** was approved by the ISO dedicated committees.

In their own words, “cities need indicators to measure their performance. Existing indicators at the local level are often not standardised, consistent, or comparable over time or across cities. This document is focused on city services and quality of life as a contribution to the sustainability of the city.

As part of a new series of International Standards being developed for a holistic and integrated approach to sustainable development, that includes indicators for city services and quality of life, indicators for smart cities and indicators for resilient cities, this set of standardised indicators provides a uniform approach to what is measured, and how that measurement is to be undertaken. As a list, it does not provide a value judgement, threshold or target numerical value for the indicators.

Conformance with this document does not confer a status in this regard. A city which conforms to this document in regards to measurement of indicators for city services and quality of life may only claim conformance to that effect.

These indicators can be used to track and monitor progress on city performance. In order to achieve sustainable development, the whole city system needs to be taken into consideration. Planning for future needs should take into consideration current use and efficiency of resources in order to better plan for tomorrow.

The indicators and associated test methods in this document have been developed in order to help cities:

a) **measure performance management** of city services and quality of life over time;

³² <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/en/#iso:std:iso:37120:ed-2:v1:en>

- b) *learn from one another by allowing comparison across a wide range of performance measures; and,*
 c) ***support policy development and priority setting.***

From these introductory words, it is already clear how similar the rationale and scope of the ISO 37120 context and SESAM are. The scope itself of the different types of indicators, for policy development and priority setting, is embodied in particular in SESAM's quantitative path. More, as a general remark, it is also well within the ambitions of SESAM to provide a standardised way to define smart rural development in an agreed and co-constructed way.

In 2019 a further development in the ISO 37120 family took place, i.e. the approval of the **ISO 37122 standard “Sustainable cities and communities — Indicators for smart cities”**³³, which displays, at the same time, a wider outlook on indicators beyond the provision of services, and a more focused approach on smartness and digitalisation as a set of tools to increase the attractiveness and guarantee the development of cities.

In their own words, ISO 37122, “*when used in conjunction with ISO 37120, helps cities to identify indicators for applying city management systems such as ISO 37101 and to **implement smart city policies, programmes and projects to:***

- *respond to challenges such as climate change, rapid population growth, and political and economic instability by fundamentally improving how they engage society;*
- *apply collaborative leadership methods, work across disciplines and city systems;*
- *use data information and modern technologies to deliver better services and quality of life to those in the city (residents, businesses, visitors);*
- *provide a better life environment where smart policies, practices and technology are put to the service of citizens;*
- *achieve their sustainability and environmental goals in a more innovative way;*
- *identify the need for and benefits of smart infrastructure;*
- *facilitate innovation and growth;*
- *build a dynamic and innovative economy ready for the challenges of tomorrow.”*

Also, in this case, remarkable similarities with the scopes and the rationale of SESAM arise, so much so that the quantitative path of SESAM was built also taking into account the dimensions, metrics and indicators included in the ISO 37122 standard for smart cities, as well as, naturally, the main conclusions and insights of the Literature Review that has led to the creation of SESAM.

The dimensions of ISO 37122, divided into several indicators, are the following: Economy, Education, Energy, Environment and Climate Change, Finance, Governance, Health, Housing, Population and Social Conditions, Recreation, Safety, Solid Waste, Sport and Culture, Telecommunication, Transportation, Urban/local Agriculture and Food Security, Urban Planning, Wastewater, Water.

³³ <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/en/#iso:std:iso:37122:ed-1:v1:en>

Clearly, ISO 37122 refers specifically to smart ‘cities’, even though it includes the somewhat more ambiguous term ‘communities’ in its title. Any connection between indicators explicitly conceived for urban areas and those that intend to be referring to rural areas needs to be cautiously pondered, with clear, specific evaluation of every single dimension, metric or indicator.

In this sense, the work of P. W. Maja and colleagues of 2020³⁴, “**Development of Smart Rural Village Indicators in line with Industry 4.0**” has been particularly useful. The Authors, in their quest to create indicators for smart rural villages that are aligned both with ISO 37122 and the Industry 4.0 concept, ask themselves the following three questions: “*Will the indicator support sustainability of rural villages? Will it be supporting smartness? Would the indicator require some form of ICT infrastructure for it to be realised?*”.

The Authors’ working definition of ‘smartness’ is a process that, simultaneously, advances the economic prospects and sustains social development in a village. The three questions allow the Authors to investigate the compatibility of the ISO 37122 indicators for rural villages. The Authors also reflect on connectivity as a possible human right, and how the smart village transition for rural areas can be subsumed in the Sustainable Development Goal 7 - Ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable and modern energy for all.

SESAM has also been constructed, in its quantitative path, on a similar manner, also taking into account the insights and indications coming from Maja et al, 2020, but with a less narrow focus on the concept of Industry 4.0, and a wider approach aiming to include as many of the original ISO 37122 dimensions’ as possible. An effort has been made in this sense for two main reasons: 1) to be adhering as close as possible to the best internationally recognised standards, and to the most recent literature on the subject of standardisation of indicators for rural areas; 2) to prepare the terrain for a possible submission of a new ISO standard, specifically designed to assess the level of smartness of rural (and in general, non-urban) areas to the ISO committees.

The latter ambition goes, by itself, beyond the scope of Smart ERA as a project, but could represent a key research topic for the project’s partnership, as well as a further, remarkably interesting output of the project itself.

In a way, the spirit and the letter of ISO 37122 has already been included in the present iteration of SESAM: its future path as a standard for rural areas is possible, but at present yet to come.

³⁴ Maja, P. W., Meyer, J., & Von Solms, S. (2020). Development of Smart Rural Village Indicators in Line with Industry 4.0. IEEE Access, 8, 152017-152033. Article 9169887. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2020.3017441>

6. SESAM within Smart ERA - relationships with other WPs and Tasks

WP2: Data-driven approaches and Macroregional Strategies

In a project as complex and elaborated as Smart ERA, the interdependency between the different work packages and the different deliverables are many and varied.

In particular, the intersections between the **Task 2.1** and the other Tasks of WP2 are the clearest and most immediate. T2.1, that has led to the creation of SESAM, the Smart ERA Smartness Assessment Method which is the object of the present document, is closely connected to **T2.2**, dedicated to data screening for designing a data-driven rural approach, and to **T2.3**, focusing on joint data-driven analyses to pilot regions.

Data-driven activities in WP2 are closely intertwined with SESAM for two reasons. First of all, any work with indicators and/or metrics implies working with data; in fact, the quantitative section of SESAM allows users to select which indicators, metrics and units of measurement (that is, data) they are able, willing to or interested in working on. Data-driven approaches also allow for a clearer setting of priorities, and a more aware selection of the decided outcomes of specific actions, in close connection with the concepts of indicators of results and indicators of performance that are themselves included in SESAM.

By extension, the use of data selected by the users, and by the pilot areas of the project in their role of the first actual users of SESAM, allow for a tailored selection and an actual co-design of actions in the six pilot areas.

By further extension, **Task 2.4**, which is dedicated to replication strategies in EU macroregions, can also benefit from SESAM by using the Smart ERA Smartness Assessment Method as an example of a rationally-constructed and newly established comprehensive methodologies to be replicated for smartness assessment purposes in the rural areas encompassed by the different EU Macroregional Strategies. In this sense, the link with EUSALP appears to be the most immediate, due to the experience of the EUSALP Macroregional Strategies with previous assessment methods, and due to the presence, within EUSALP, of a cross-sectoral strategy explicitly dedicated to the smart village-smart community concept. That said, also the other Macroregional Strategies included in Smart ERA could benefit from SESAM, and could also contribute to its further refinement and expansion.

WP3: Co-design of the Smartness Innovation Packages (SIP)

Beyond WP2, there are clear links between SESAM and several tasks included in **WP3**, dedicated to the co-design of Smart Innovation Packages (SIP) for rural innovation and sustaining community participation. More specifically, close links have been built with **Task 3.1** on co-design methodology for rural innovation and SIPs' development, that in fact is being constructed at the same time as SESAM.

The collaboration is ongoing on the significant synergies that can emerge between SESAM and the SIPs, with the present framework being in fact twofold: 1) SESAM will represent one of the canvases of the Smart Innovation Packages, supporting the collaborative activities of the stakeholders and actors in the pilot areas; SESAM, together with its sister assessment methods could perfectly fit as new ingredients/cards (or "family" card) in the category of resources that help stakeholders acquire knowledge on the potential and priorities in pilot areas within the development and the application of the SIP Toolkits. 2) Specific smartness assessment methods, collected during the Literature Review leading to SESAM, and with less broad and more specific focus (i.e. on economy, tourism, mobility, ...) could represent, by themselves, specific ingredients/cards of the SIP, to be selected and applied by pilot areas and other users to define their own priorities and select actions in their specific area of interest.

In the same context, important synergies can be found with **Task 3.3**, which focuses on the co-design of Smart Innovation Packages to empower rural communities. In this case, a coherent and consistent application of SESAM, as a special canvas in the SIP Toolkit, will be created in the context of the actual co-design and implementation of the Smart Innovation Packages for rural areas, to identify and map needs and expectations, as well as necessary data sources, in relation to the most urgent challenge(s), vulnerable sector(s) and socio-economic and environmental trends of their territories.

WP4: Data dashboard for rural smartness assessment analysis

Close relationships have also been built between SESAM/Task 2.1 and the **WP4**, dedicated to the development and integration of SIPs technological components.

More in detail, SESAM's qualitative path, including the emotional mapping, has already been subsumed into **Task 4.2**, that has focused on the creation of a data dashboard for rural smartness assessment analysis. In close cooperation with the partners of WP4, and in particular with the University of Maribor, the qualitative path of SESAM has already been made available for pilot areas, allowing them to identify the dimensions in which they wish to work in the quantitative path, and challenging them to experiment with the emotional mapping of their own territories.

Synergies with **Task 4.3**, dedicated to the SIPs' technological components development and integration, will also be paramount, especially in the context of the need of having SESAM available online in an accessible and usable format.

WP5, WP6 and WP7: Community Engagement, Policy Analyses and Communication

Relationships that are perhaps less immediate, but still relevant, are being sought between SESAM/Task 2.1 and Smart ERA's **WP5**, dedicated to Community engagement, piloting and testing, **WP6**, working on Policy analyses and recommendations, and **WP7**, the project's Communication, dissemination, exploitation and macro-regional networking activities.

In general terms, SESAM's relationship with **WP5** is rather straightforward: SESAM, in its qualitative and/or quantitative paths, will be submitted to all pilot areas for feedbacks, applications, monitoring and further directions. A dialogue in this sense has already been established, and discussions are ongoing on how to make the actual use of SESAM more user-friendly and readily applicable in all pilot areas.

As regards **WP6**, and its work on policies and recommendations, the main findings of **Task 6.1** - Guidelines for policy audit and identification of key concepts and policy options have been incorporated in SESAM's dimension 'Governance and Policies' in order for the dimension's indicators to be as close as possible to the key concepts and policy options identified in Task 6.1.

As per **WP7**, all efforts will be made to disseminate SESAM internally, and to communicate about the work of Task 2.1 also outside the partnership to other potentially interested areas.

7. Closing remarks and the way ahead

The **way ahead** for SESAM and Task 2.1, in terms of the activities within Smart ERA and its relationships with the project's further work in WPs from 2 to 7, has been described and discussed in the previous chapter: from the meeting in Milan on December 3 and 4 2024 SESAM represents a shared project deliverable, and its contribution to the rest of the project activities is ready to be put to test, improved, further clarified. As mentioned before, in fact, the use and validation of SESAM in the project's **pilot areas**, depending on which path they choose, is of paramount importance, as well as SESAM's incorporation and dynamic relationship with the **SIP**.

Future developments will include participation in **conferences** focused on Smart Villages, Smart Rural Areas and Smart Mountains, the production of **peer-reviewed papers** on SESAM by the Smart ERA partnership, covering literature reviews, results, dedicated Smart Village indicators, and the SESAM assessment methodology with its underlying rationale, and the potential inclusion of SESAM in a dedicated **Smart Villages publication**, which is currently in the early stages of submission to Springer Eds. and preparation for the review process.

In 2020, Maja and colleagues concluded their work on the development of smart rural village indicators in line with Industry 4.0 with the following remarks: *“The conclusion s that a smart village should sustain itself, be smart and be able to connect to the outside world both in terms of ICT networks and via physical road/rail infrastructures (...). We agree that the indicators developed need to be implemented as a case study for validating. (...). Hence, we recommend that for future studies. This is to say longitudinal studies to be done to test the validity of the indicators proposed in this article. We further recommend that an ISO standard similar to the ISO standard on smart cities indicators be developed, and the list of indicators be used as initial input to developing such a standard for policy makers across the world.”*

SESAM, and Smart ERA in general, are in the position to respond to the final remarks of that seminal paper, and are open to become a first important step as a case study for **validating new indicators** (and new dimensions, and new metrics), also in order to establish an ambitious standard, and **possibly a new ISO standard**, for smart villages and smart rural areas. The exploration of ways to pursue this ambitious path will be part of the nearest future of Smart ERA's SESAM.

Annex 1

SESAM Qualitative questionnaire

As part of our ongoing efforts within the SMART ERA project, we are developing SESAM (Smart Era Smartness Assessment Method), a reference model aimed at evaluating the "smartness" of rural communities and villages across Europe. SESAM is designed to offer a comprehensive qualitative and quantitative analysis of the factors that contribute to the smart development of a given territory.

This questionnaire focuses specifically on qualitatively assessing smartness in rural communities. It addresses six key dimensions of villages and communities' level of smartness: 1) Enabling Factors (digital infrastructure and digital literacy); 2) Mobility; 3) Governance and Policies; 4) Economy); 5) Services of general interest; 6) Environment and environmental and climate-related SDGs. These dimensions were identified through a Literature Review on Smartness Assessment Methods and compiled in the Intermediate Report for D2.1 – Analysis and Insights for Task 2.1.

General information

Estimated time of completion:

..... mins

About the villages and rural communities:

Name of the village/community
Region
Country

About the participant:

Number of stakeholders participating in the survey:
Institutions:
Fields of work ³⁵ :
.....

³⁵ Based on the ESCO Classification of Occupations

Instructions for Survey Participants:

- **Collective Participation:** This survey is intended to be completed by community members together. Engaging in discussions with others helps ensure a well-rounded perspective.
- **Rating Scale:** For each item, participants are asked to evaluate its relevance or effectiveness using a scale ranging from the lowest to the highest value (five levels).
- **Thoughtful Responses:** In addition to rating each item, participants are encouraged to provide written responses in the designated spaces, sharing their experiences and perspectives on the community. These qualitative responses are invaluable for understanding local views.

Enabling Factors

Digital Infrastructure refers to the physical hardware and software technologies that enable digital services. It encompasses the IT systems and networks that allow organizations to operate and communicate, as well as the equitable access and use of these technologies. Key components of digital infrastructure include hardware, software, networks, data centers, cloud computing, and cybersecurity systems. In line with the European Parliament and Council's 2006 Recommendation, in order to make profitable uses of digital infrastructures, specific competences are needed. They are defined as the ability to confidently and critically use information society technologies (IST) for work, leisure, and communication. These competencies are grounded in basic ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) skills, such as retrieving, evaluating, storing, producing, presenting, and exchanging information, as well as communicating and participating in collaborative networks via the Internet.

Questions

- **How would you assess the availability and quality of mobile internet connectivity in your rural community, considering factors such as access to free Wi-Fi, mobile coverage, and areas with limited or no signal ('blank spots')?** Please explain your rating and share any challenges or benefits you've experienced.
 - Very poor
 - Poor
 - Acceptable
 - Good
 - Very good

- **How would you assess the availability and quality of fixed internet (e.g., broadband, fiber) in your rural community?** Consider aspects such as speed, reliability, and accessibility. Please explain your rating and share any challenges or benefits you've experienced.

- Very poor
 - Poor
 - Acceptable
 - Good
 - Very good
-
-
-

- **How would you consider the cost of communication services (e.g., mobile, fixed internet) in your community, considering the effectiveness and efficiency of the services provided?** Please explain your reasoning and share any specific challenges or benefits you've encountered.

- Very low
 - Low
 - Moderate
 - High
 - Very high
-
-
-

- **How would you describe your community's ability to access, understand, and effectively use digital information and content?** Please explain your reasoning and highlight any specific challenges or strengths your community faces.

- Very low
 - Low
 - Moderate
 - High
 - Very high
-
-
-

- **How frequently does your community participate in political or social discussions online, and through which platforms or methods (e.g., email, social media, forums, messaging apps)?** Please provide examples and describe the level of engagement.

- Never
- Seldom
- Sometimes
- Often
- Almost always

-
-
-
- **How familiar is your community with tools for creating digital content in various formats (e.g., text, images, video, or audio) for daily use?** How do you assess this familiarity, and can you provide any examples?
 - Unfamiliar
 - Slightly familiar
 - Moderately familiar
 - Very familiar
 - Expert
-
-
-

Metrics

- **Which enabling factors related to digital infrastructure and literacy are most important for you to monitor?** Please rate each option on a scale from 1 (Not important) to 5 (Very important).
 - Access to high-speed internet
 - Availability of public Wi-Fi hotspots
 - Digital literacy levels among the population
 - Access to digital training programs
 - Usage rates of digital services (e.g., e-governance, online education)
 - Availability of digital devices (e.g., smartphones, computers)
 - Community engagement in digital initiatives
 - Infrastructure for digital entrepreneurship
 - **Are there any other indicators related to enabling factors that you believe would be important to track? Please specify:**
-
-
-

Mobility and Transport

While transportation can be described as the act of moving goods or people, mobility underlines the act or the ability of a person to be moved. Mobility isn't just about having access to one mode of transportation but having the ability to access these services and the quality of those options. As the EU moves rapidly towards a more sustainable, smart, and inclusive mobility and transport sector, rural areas must also adapt to these changes. The EU's focus is on creating an interconnected, efficient, and environmentally friendly transport system that serves all citizens, including those in remote or rural areas. Digitalisation plays

a key role in this transition, enabling innovative solutions like on-demand bus services, vehicle sharing programs, and optimised public transport routes.

This section aims to assess the current state of mobility and transport in your rural community, identify areas for improvement, and explore how much space there is for new technologies and smart policies in this sector.

Questions

- **How would you assess the current state of transport infrastructure in your village (e.g., roads, railways, bus stops, cycle lanes)? What specific factors—such as maintenance, accessibility, or convenience—influence your assessment? Please explain your reasoning and share any key examples or experiences**

- Very poor
 - Poor
 - Acceptable
 - Good
 - Very good
-
-
-

- **Think about the public transport services in your area. Do you believe they are efficient and well-organized? Why or why not? Consider factors such as timeliness, coverage, reliability, and user experience in your response**

- Strongly Disagree
 - Disagree
 - Undecided
 - Agree
 - Strongly Agree
-
-
-

- **How would you assess the condition and upkeep of public transportation means (trains, buses, car/bike-sharing, etc.) in your village, and what factors contribute to your rating?**

- Very poor
 - Poor
 - Acceptable
 - Good
 - Very good
-
-
-

- **How frequently do you think your community rely on private means of transportation (e.g., cars, motorcycles) for daily commute or errands in your villages, and why?**
 - Never
 - Rarely
 - Sometimes
 - Very Often
 - Always
-
-
-

Metrics

- **Which of the following mobility-related data points are most important for you to track?** Please rate each option on a scale from 1 (Not important) to 5 (Very important).
 - Public transport usage
 - Electric vehicle adoption
 - Traffic congestion levels
 - Cycling and walking infrastructure
 - Average commute times
 - Car-sharing and ride-hailing service usage
 - Pedestrian walkability
 - Environmental impact (e.g., emissions reduction)
 - Cost-efficiency for citizens
 - Convenience and accessibility
 - Car ownership rates between regions
 - Bike-sharing program usage
 - Growth in electric vehicle use
 - Traffic density across tourist seasons
- **Are there any other Indicators related to infrastructure and mobility that you believe would be important to track? Please specify:**

Economy

Economic activities are generally divided into three main sectors. This survey focuses on those most commonly associated with rural areas:

- **Primary Sector:** Activities that involve extracting or harvesting resources from the Earth, such as agriculture, livestock farming, forestry, fishing, aquaculture, mining, and quarrying.
- **Secondary Sector:** Specifically focusing on energy production in rural contexts.

- Tertiary Sector: Services provided to individuals or enterprises, especially those related to tourism, and business services activities.

The aim of the following questions is to encourage participants to reflect on the various income-generating activities in rural areas, including those they are currently involved in or plan to pursue. Consider the challenges and opportunities rural economic activities face, and the availability of financial resources to support the digital transformation of these sectors. It's important to acknowledge that not all activities are viable in every context or location.

Questions

- **How important are agriculture, forestry, fishing, aquaculture, mining, quarrying activities in your community?** Describe their role in the local economy, considering aspects like employment, income generation, and cultural importance.

- Not Important
 - Slightly Important
 - Moderately Important
 - Important
 - Very important
-
-
-

- **How common is it in your community to produce renewable energy through small-scale production systems (e.g., solar panels, wind turbines, small hydro systems, or biomass), and what types of systems are being used?**

- Very uncommon
 - Somewhat uncommon
 - Moderately common
 - Common
 - Very common
-
-
-

- **Does your community or household use energy storage systems (e.g., home batteries, community-scale storage) to store excess energy? If yes, why was it necessary?**

- Not used or needed
- Rarely used and optional
- Moderately used and helpful
- Often used and beneficial
- Widely used and essential

-
-
-
- Reflect on the economic impact tourism has on your community, considering both direct and indirect contributions, as well as the types of tourism activities prevalent in the area (e.g., cultural, eco-tourism, adventure tourism, etc.). **How has tourism contributed to your local economy and why?**
 - Insignificant or non-existent
 - Limited and supplementary
 - Moderate and beneficial
 - Important and growing
 - Significant and transformative
-
-
-

- **How would you assess the growth of the ICT sector over the past decade in your community? Do you believe it is gaining prominence, and if so, why?**
 - Very slow growth
 - Slow growth
 - Moderate growth
 - Significant growth
 - Rapid growth
-
-
-

- Reflect on the challenges faced by your community or business in accessing financial resources that are aimed at enabling digital transformation in rural areas. Consider the availability of loans, grants, or other forms of financial support tailored for rural digital initiatives. **How would you assess the difficulty in obtaining financial support (e.g., loans) linked to digital transformation in your local economy and why?**
 - Not Important
 - Slightly Important
 - Moderately Important
 - Important
 - Very Important
-
-
-

Metrics

- **Which economic data related to the three main sectors would you find most valuable for improving productivity and decision-making?** Please rate each option on a scale from 1 (Not valuable) to 5 (Very valuable).
 - Crop yield data
 - Soil quality and fertility levels
 - Weather and climate conditions
 - Pest and disease outbreaks
 - Market prices for agricultural products
 - Water availability and usage
 - Production volumes of local agri-food products (e.g., olive oil, wine)
 - Economic data on the local agri-food sector (revenues, exports)
 - Visitor numbers and trends
 - Revenue generated from tourism
 - Sustainable tourism initiatives (e.g., eco-tourism)
 - Tourist satisfaction surveys
 - Impact of tourism on local resources
 - Renewable energy usage (e.g., solar, wind)

- **Are there any other economic Indicators related the three main economic sectors that you believe would be important to track? Please specify:**

Governance and Policy

This module helps to assess the digital maturity of governance and policy within public administrations. Governance refers to the political and institutional frameworks provided by both public and non-public entities, as well as the collaborative dynamics between key stakeholders—including external actors and those directly benefiting from development initiatives. It also considers how policies are formulated and implemented to support digital transformation. The section is structured around the following dimensions:

- **Public Governance:** Evaluates the level of support and involvement from public actors in driving rural development and digitalization within the community.
- **Non-Governmental Support:** Investigates the role of non-public entities, such as civil society organizations (CSOs) and research institutions, in contributing to rural development and digital initiatives.

- **Policy Development and Implementation:** Focuses on the creation, adaptation, and execution of policies that promote digital transition, including policies that address societal challenges, such as privacy, security, and equitable access.

The module also explores how effectively policies and governance mechanisms coordinate across different sectors to support digital transformation, as well as the capacity of institutions to implement these policies and monitor progress.

To assess smart governance and policy in your area, please answer the following questions

Questions

- **Reflect on any digital programs or initiatives launched or supported by local schools, libraries, healthcare institutions, or government offices. Consider aspects such as infrastructure development, training programs, or funding opportunities for digital projects. Which kind of support public institutions provide to aid digital initiatives in your community and how?**
 - Very little support
 - Limited support
 - Moderate support
 - Significant support
 - Full support
-
-
-

- **Consider the extent to which your local government leaders advocate for digital policies, allocate funding, or partner with stakeholders to drive digital transformation. Reflect on public speeches, strategies, or campaigns that focus on digitalization. What role do local government leaders play in promoting digital transformation?**
 - No role
 - Minimal role
 - Moderate role
 - Active role
 - Leading role
-
-
-

- **Think about the presence of local NGOs, associations, or community groups that work to promote digital literacy, provide technology access, or encourage digital inclusion. What role do civil society organizations (CSOs) play in supporting digital initiatives in your community and how they do it?**
 - No role
 - Minimal role
 - Moderate role
 - Active role
 - Leading role
-
-
-

- **Consider how well digital initiatives are coordinated across different sectors (e.g., education, health, transport, etc.) in your community. Are digital policies consistent and aligned across various governance siloes and why?**
 - Not integrated at all
 - Slightly integrated
 - Moderately integrated
 - Well integrated
 - Fully integrated
-
-
-

Metrics

- **Which of the following governance-related information would you find most valuable? Please rate each option on a scale from 1 (Not valuable) to 5 (Very valuable).**
 - Public spending and budget allocation
 - E-governance services usage
 - Citizen participation in decision-making processes
 - Public satisfaction with local government services
 - Legislation and policy changes that impact the region
- **Are there any other Indicators related to governance and policy information that you believe would be important to track? Please specify:**

Services of general interest

Universal access to essential services such as healthcare, education and other general services is a core mandate for European countries. However, factors like shrinking budgets, depopulation, and ageing societies make it increasingly difficult to provide these services—particularly in rural areas where costs and accessibility challenges are greater. Ensuring reliable access to these services is crucial for helping rural areas thrive, making them more attractive and viable for residents.

This section on the survey is structured around three key dimensions:

- **Healthcare:** Health services are vital to society and the economy. Healthcare is recognized as a basic human right, essential for safeguarding the health and safety of populations. It includes various components of a healthcare system, such as hospitals, vaccination programs, clinics, and the personnel who run the system (doctors, nurses, managers, pharmacists, etc.).
- **Education:** Education involves the transmission of knowledge, skills, and character traits, taking place in both formal and informal settings, both of which are crucial for community development. In its infrastructural aspect, it includes the physical entities and facilities of schools, classrooms, laboratories, etc., while in its organizational aspect, it includes curricular materials, student assessments, administrative procedures, and learning routines.
- **General Services:** These encompass essential functions that support the daily needs of residents in rural communities, including postal services, banking, and local government services.

Questions

- Think about the proximity and quality of the nearest healthcare facilities, including hospitals, clinics, and emergency services. Reflect on how quickly healthcare services respond in urgent situations and the overall effectiveness of healthcare interventions in your community. **How do you believe the healthcare system is functioning in your community, and why?**
 - Very poor functions
 - Poor functions
 - Acceptable functions
 - Good functions
 - Very good functions

- **Do you believe that improved access to telemedicine or online healthcare services could significantly benefit your community? Why or why not?**

- Strongly Disagree
 - Disagree
 - Undecided
 - Agree
 - Strongly Agree
-
-
-

- Think about the proximity and quality of the nearest educational facilities, including schools, training centers, and learning resources. Reflect on how accessible educational services are, the timeliness of support for students, and the overall effectiveness of educational interventions in your community. **How do you believe the education system is functioning in your community, and why?**

- Very poor functions
 - Poor functions
 - Acceptable functions
 - Good functions
 - Very good functions
-
-
-

- **Do you believe that improved access to online education platforms or digital learning resources could significantly benefit your community? Why or why not?**

- Strongly Disagree
 - Disagree
 - Undecided
 - Agree
 - Strongly Agree
-
-
-

- Think about the proximity and quality of the nearest general services, including postal services, banking facilities, and local government services. Reflect on how accessible these services are, the timeliness of their response to community needs, and the overall effectiveness of these services in supporting daily life in your community. **How do you believe the general service system is functioning in your community, and why?**

- Very poor functions
 - Poor functions
 - Acceptable functions
 - Good functions
 - Very good functions
-
-
-

- **Do you believe that improved access to online resources and digital services (e.g., online banking, e-government services, postal tracking, or digital public services) could significantly benefit your community? Why or why not?**
 - Strongly Disagree
 - Disagree
 - Undecided
 - Agree
 - Strongly Agree
-
-
-

Metrics

- **Which aspects of services would you find most valuable to visualize on the dashboard?** Please rate each option on a scale from 1 (Not valuable) to 5 (Very valuable).
 - Housing affordability and availability
 - Access to healthcare services
 - Quality of education and schools
 - Crime rates and safety data
 - Cultural and recreational opportunities
 - Cost of living (e.g., rents, groceries, utilities)
 - **Are there any other Indicators or indicators related to community services that you believe would be important to track? Please specify:**
-
-
-

Environment and Environmental and Climate-Related SDGs

This dimension centres on the crucial theme of environmental sustainability, anchored in the "planet" cluster of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. As highlighted by the European Environmental Agency, this cluster underscores the imperative to protect our planet from degradation through sustainable consumption and production practices, responsible management of natural resources, and urgent action against climate change.

In rural areas, the impacts of these environmental challenges can be particularly acute, affecting both local communities and their ecosystems. This dimension aims to delve into the specific ways rural regions are grappling with these pressing issues. We seek to understand how they can actively safeguard and conserve their natural resources, foster a green and resource-efficient economy, and protect their citizens from environmental risks that jeopardize health and well-being.

The questions in this section prioritize key areas such as:

- The protection, conservation, and enhancement of natural capital;
- The mitigation of environmental pressures and risks to health and well-being in rural communities;
- The development of a resource-efficient, low-carbon economy.

Questions

- Consider the natural resources in your village, such as forests, rivers, wildlife, and protected areas. Reflect on the local initiatives focused on conservation, the preservation of green spaces, and the promotion of sustainable land use. **To what extent does your community actively contribute to the protection and sustainable management of local natural resources, and how they do that?**
 - Not at all
 - A little
 - Moderately
 - Considerably
 - Extensively

- Reflect on the occurrence of extreme weather events in your area and consider the local projects aimed at addressing climate change risks such as flooding, drought, and heat stress. **Do you believe your community is making sufficient efforts to tackle these challenges effectively, and why?**
 - Not at all
 - A little

- Moderately
 - Considerably
 - Extensively
-
-
-

- Reflect on how your community manages waste—whether solid, liquid, or organic—both from households and the local economic sector. Consider the presence of recycling and waste management programs, such as composting initiatives and zero-waste strategies. **To what extent does your community actively contribute to the sustainable management of waste, and how they do that?**

- Not at all
 - A little
 - Moderately
 - Considerably
 - Extensively
-
-
-

- Reflect on sustainable agriculture practices, water management strategies and green building initiatives. **How would you assess your community's progress in developing a resource-efficient, low-carbon economy and why?**

- Not Important
 - Slightly Important
 - Moderately Important
 - Important
 - Very Important
-
-
-

Metrics

- **Which of the following environmental factors and sustainability indicators are most important for you to monitor?** Please rate each option on a scale from 1 (Not important) to 5 (Very important).
 - Air quality
 - Water quality and availability
 - Green spaces and biodiversity
 - Renewable energy production
 - Waste and recycling rates

- Carbon emissions
- Tracking climate change adaptation measures
- Water conservation efforts
- Biodiversity and wildlife protection
- Green transportation (e.g., electric vehicles, cycling infrastructure)
- Sustainable agricultural practices

- **Are there any other indicators related to environmental factors and sustainability that you believe would be important to track? Please specify:**

Annex 2

Emotional Mapping

As part of our ongoing efforts within the SMART ERA project, we are developing SESAM (Smart Era Smartness Assessment Method), a reference model aimed at evaluating the "smartness" of rural communities and villages across Europe. SESAM is designed to offer a comprehensive qualitative and quantitative analysis of the factors that contribute to the smart development of a given territory.

General information

Estimated time of completion:

..... mins

About the villages and rural communities:

Name of the village/community
Region
Country

About the participant:

Number of stakeholders participating in the survey:
Institutions:
Fields of work ³⁶ :
.....

Instructions for Emotional Mapping Participants

Participants are invited to map collective emotions related to the six key dimensions of rural "smartness" by following these steps:

1. Prepare a Print of the Map Area

- Use a web service (e.g., Google Maps, Bing Maps) to print a detailed map of the area you are assessing.
- The map scale should be clear for easy identification of areas. Ensure the map is printed on an appropriately sized paper (e.g., A2 or A1) using an international standard size.

³⁶ Based on the ESCO Classification of Occupations

- The background of the map should be neutral (not colourful) to facilitate the marking of emotions using different colours.

2. Identify Emotional Responses

Reflect emotions based on Paul Ekman's universal identification of basic emotions. It serves as the foundation for understanding emotional responses. Below are operative explanations for these emotions and some extended ones.

Table 5. Basic emotions: function and manifestation

Emotion	Function	Manifestation
Happiness	Reinforces behaviours that benefit well-being and strengthen social bonds.	Smiling, laughter, and increased energy.
Sadness	Signals a loss or need for support, fostering social connection and empathy.	Tearfulness, withdrawal, and low energy.
Disgust	Protects from harmful substances or situations, both physical and moral.	Wrinkling the nose, turning away, revulsion.
Fear	Alerts to danger and triggers survival mechanisms like fight, flight, or freeze.	Increased heart rate, wide eyes, and alertness.
Surprise	Draws attention to unexpected events and prompts quick adaptation.	Raised eyebrows, open mouth, sudden focus.
Anger	Motivates action to overcome obstacles or address perceived injustices.	Frowning, raised voice, and physical tension.

This Emotional mapping focuses specifically on qualitatively assessing smartness in rural communities. It addresses six key dimensions of villages and communities' level of smartness.

Table 6. SESAM dimensions and topics

Dimensions	Sub-dimensions	Manifestation
Enabling Factors	digital infrastructure and digital literacy	This dimension underpins the digital transformation of rural areas by ensuring equitable access to digital infrastructure and fostering digital literacy. It emphasizes the importance of robust physical and virtual systems (e.g., broadband, cybersecurity) and skills development to empower individuals and communities to engage effectively in the digital era.
Mobility and Transport	Technical and information infrastructure; Mobility methods and vehicles used for this purpose; Legislation	Focuses on creating accessible, efficient, and environmentally sustainable transport systems tailored to rural needs. Through smart technologies such as real-time tracking and shared mobility solutions, this dimension addresses challenges like low population density and long travel distances, bridging urban-rural mobility gaps.

Economy	Three-sector model of the economy	Aims to boost the resilience and sustainability of rural economies through innovation and smart practices. It encompasses: Primary Sector: Sustainable agriculture, livestock, and resource harvesting. Secondary Sector: Energy production with an emphasis on renewable solutions. Tertiary Sector: Tourism and advanced services fostering economic vitality and digital inclusion.
Smart Governance and Policy	Public Governance; Non-Governmental Support; Policy Development and Implementation	Explores the role of governance and collaborative policies in rural innovation. It evaluates the contributions of public entities, non-governmental organizations, and policy frameworks to drive digital transformation and address societal challenges while ensuring equitable resource allocation.
Services of General Interest (SGIs)	Healthcare; Education; General Services	Addresses the provision of essential services like healthcare, education, and general public utilities in rural areas. By leveraging smart solutions (e.g., eHealth, IoT), it enhances accessibility, reliability, and inclusivity, ensuring a high quality of life and community cohesion.
Environment and ClimateRelated SDGs	Protection, Conservation, and Enhancement of Natural Capital; Mitigation of Environmental Pressures and Risks; Development of a Resource-Efficient, Low-Carbon Economy	Centres on achieving environmental sustainability through: Preserving biodiversity and ecosystems; Reducing pollution and adapting to climate change; Advancing renewable energy and circular practices to ensure a greener, more resource-efficient future.

Consider how these emotions relate to each of the six SESAM dimensions within your community. For example:

- How do you feel about the state of public transport (Mobility and Transport)?
- What emotions arise when thinking about digital infrastructure (Enabling Factors)?

3. Assess the Spatial Extent of Emotions

When connected to the SESAM framework's six dimensions, emotions provide insights into how individuals and communities perceive, adapt to, and interact with their surroundings. Determine if the emotions are tied to specific object (e.g., a cycleway, building) or locations (e.g., a school, park) or if they span broader areas of the community and try to build a chart similar to the chart that follow.

Table 7. SESAM qualitative framework: part 1

SESAM Dimensions	Object	Location	Response	Emotion
Enabling Factors	Investment	First street in the ABC village	Anger
Mobility and Transport	New cycleway	Second crossroads in the ABC village	Happiness

Economy	Tomato's market	Third street in the ABC village	Surprise
Governance and Policy	Smart reform	Fourth crossroads in the ABC village	Fear
Services of General Interest (SGIs)	Healthcare system	Fifth street in the ABC village	Sadness
Environment and Climate-Related SDGs	Waste	Sixth crossroads in the ABC village	Disgust

4. Place Emotions on the Map

- Using the printed map, mark locations that elicit strong emotional responses.
- Use distinct colours to represent different emotions and make a legend (e.g., green for happiness, red for frustration).

5. Describe the Emotions

- For each marked location, describe the response of specific emotions felt by your community.
- Explain why these emotions are present at that location and what factors influence them.

Table 8. SESAM qualitative framework: part 2

SESAM Dimensions	Object	Location	Response	Emotion
Enabling Factors	Investment	First street in the ABC village	<i>Frustration when an infrastructural</i>	Anger

			<i>broadband project is interrupted due to a lack of investments....</i>	
Mobility and Transport	New cycleway	Second crossroads in the ABC village	<i>Cycling along the newly created agricultural cycleway, developed with European funding, feels truly rewarding and uplifting....</i>	Happiness
Economy	Tomato's market	Third street in the ABC village	<i>Receiving unexpected good news about improved production performance following the adoption of digital tools....</i>	Surprise
Governance and Policy	Smart reform	Fourth crossroads in the ABC village	<i>Anxiety about a conservative leadership change affect smart innovative strategies....</i>	Fear
Services of General Interest (SGIs)	Healthcare system	Fifth street in the ABC village	<i>Sadness when elderly residents in rural areas cannot access essential public services, like healthcare, due to limited transportation options and poor connectivity....</i>	Sadness
Environment and Climate-Related SDGs	Waste	Sixth crossroads in the ABC village	<i>Reacting to illegal waste disposal practices....</i>	Disgust

6. Review the Emotional Map

- Examine the completed map for patterns, clusters, or gaps in emotional responses.
- Discuss these findings with other participants to gain a broader understanding of the emotional and spatial landscape.

7. Engage in Collective Reflection

- Discuss your observations with other participants to explore the emotional landscape collectively.
- Reflect on how these shared emotions may influence the community's understanding of its current situation and future aspirations

Annex 3

Enabling Factors: Indicators and metrics

Indicator list

Table 9. Enabling Factors - Indicators and their prioritization

Dimensions	Sub-dimensions	Indicators	Definitions	Total score	Veto Factor
Enabling factors	Digital infrastructure	Level of Digital Connectivity	Measures the availability and quality of digital network connections within a rural community.		
		Level of Analog Connectivity	Assesses traditional, non-digital means of connectivity (e.g., postal services, telephony) to gauge infrastructure inclusivity in areas with limited digital access.		
		Computational Capacity Potential	Evaluates the available computing resources and potential for scaling digital capabilities within rural areas.		
		Economic Accessibility of Internet Services	Examines the affordability and economic accessibility of internet services for rural residents, aiming to highlight potential barriers to digital engagement.		
	Digital literacy	Technical Proficiency of Rural Populations	Evaluates the ICT skill levels within rural communities,		

			reflecting their capability to leverage digital tools effectively.		
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Self-assessment

Before proceeding with the ranking process, participants are encouraged to carefully consider the following questions:

- What is the relative significance of each indicator in achieving the objectives of the selected project?
- How does each specific indicator contribute to the success and long-term sustainability of the project?

Rank each pair of indicators in the pairwise matrix below based on preference, using the scoring system provided. The scale ranges from 1 to 3:

- “One” indicates that the two indicators are equally important;
- “Two” indicates that one indicator is moderately more important than the other;
- “Three” indicates that one indicator is significantly more important than the other.

For each pair of indicators choose a value from 1 to 3. A 3 or 2 to the left column chart shows that the statement on the left is significantly or moderately more important than the one on the right, while a 2 or 3 to the right column chart indicates that the statement on the right is moderately or significantly more important than the one on the left.

Table 10. Enabling Factors - pairwise matrix

	3	2	1	2	3	
Level of Digital Connectivity						Computational Capacity Potential
Level of Digital Connectivity						Economic Accessibility of Internet Services
Level of Digital Connectivity						Technical Proficiency of Rural Populations
Level of Analog Connectivity						Computational Capacity Potential
Level of Analog Connectivity						Economic Accessibility of Internet Services

Level of Analog Connectivity						Technical Proficiency of Rural Populations
Computational Capacity Potential						Economic Accessibility of Internet Services
Computational Capacity Potential						Technical Proficiency of Rural Populations
Economic Accessibility of Internet Services						Technical Proficiency of Rural Populations

Completing all pairwise comparisons, participants calculate the **total score** for each indicator using “points” across the rows. The values should be added with a positive or negative sign based on the indicator's position in the matrix.

After finalizing the ranking of indicators, reflect on the **essential indicators** that directly impact the project's core objectives and feasibility.

- Any indicator that directly influences the project's success or its ability to meet legal, technical, or environmental requirements should be considered as a **Veto Factor**.
- If any indicator is flagged as a Veto Factor, it must be treated with utmost importance in the decision-making process, even if its ranking in the pairwise comparison is lower than others.
- When completing the ranking and prioritization of indicators, stakeholders should ensure that the Veto Factor is integrated into the final decision.

Metrics, units, importance and sources

Table 11. Enabling Factors – Metrics and their units

Status indicators	Metric	Units	Importance/Definition	Sources
Level of Digital Connectivity	Ratio of backbone fiber length to households	(km/households)	Fiber backbone supports the necessary quality of experience and reliability broadband services need. So, a higher amount of backbone fiber per household drives greater reliability and performance for broadband networks.	Global Fiber Development Index: 2020
Level of Digital Connectivity	Cells site density per km ²	(Number/ km ²)	All equipment (antenna, building and ground) used to transmit cell signals to and from the mobile device back to the receiver. They're absolutely vital to the wireless infrastructure that powers rural areas.	Horanont, T., Phiboonbanakit, T., & Phithakkitnukoon, S. (2018). Resembling Population Density Distribution with Massive Mobile Phone Data. <i>Data Science Journal</i> , 17, 24. https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2018-024
Computational Capacity Potential	Data centers capacity per km ²	(kW/km ²)	This indicator measures the total computational capacity (in teraflops or petaflops) of data centers located within a rural area, normalized by the total land area (in square kilometers) of that area. It assesses the density of computational resources available, highlighting the potential for technological applications, data processing, and digital services in rural communities.
Economic Accessibility of Internet Services	Average of monthly cost of broadband and mobile internet services per household	(€/household)	The Broadband Internet Cost indicator measures the average monthly cost that households pay for broadband and mobile internet services. This value is expressed in euros per household (€/household) and provides insights into the affordability and accessibility of internet	Broadband statistics OECD https://www.oecd.org/en/topics/sub-issues/broadband-statistics.html

				services within a rural region or community.	
Level of Connectivity	Analog	Percentage of households with access to traditional telephone lines	%	This metric measures the proportion of rural households that have access to traditional telephony. In many rural communities, where digital infrastructure may be underdeveloped, analog communication remains a primary means of connectivity.	
Level of Connectivity	Analog	Percentage of households with access to regular postal service.	%	This metric measures the proportion of rural households that have access to postal services. In many rural communities, where digital infrastructure may be underdeveloped, analog communication remains a primary means of connectivity.	
Level of Analog Connectivity		Number of Post Boxes per Square Km	(Number/km ²)	This metric represents the density of post boxes available within a given area, calculated as the total number of post boxes divided by the total land area (in square kilometers). It serves as an indicator of the accessibility and availability of basic postal services in a region. In rural areas, the availability of post boxes can significantly affect community connectivity and access to essential services, particularly for residents in remote locations.	ECONOMICS OF POSTAL SERVICES: Report to the European Commission DG-MARKT Prepared by NERA July 2004, London: https://ec.europa.eu/pressroom/documents/14108/attachments/1/translations/en/renditions/pdf
Level of Analog Connectivity		Percentage of consumers receiving reliable local radio broadcasts.	%	This metric assesses the extent to which local radio broadcasts reach rural communities reliably. Radio remains a widely accessible and effective medium for communication, particularly in areas where internet access is limited or sporadic. Local radio broadcasts often include relevant information on weather, public announcements, emergency alerts, and community events. The metric is expressed as the percentage of the rural area that receives consistent and clear radio signals from local stations.	Rice, S. (2022). Importance of Digital Terrestrial Television and Broadcast Radio Ipsos. https://www.ipsos.com/en-uk/importance-digital-terrestrial-television-and-broadcast-radio
Level of Connectivity	Analog	Percentage of consumers receiving	%	This metric assesses the extent to which local or	Rice, S. (2022). Importance of Digital

		television exclusively through over-the-air broadcast signals		national over-the-air broadcast television signals reach rural communities. Television remains a widely accessible and effective medium for communication, particularly in areas where internet access or cable is limited or sporadic. The metric is expressed as the percentage of the rural area that receives exclusively over-the-air broadcast signals.	Terrestrial Television and Broadcast Radio Ipsos. https://www.ipsos.com/en-uk/importance-digital-terrestrial-television-and-broadcast-radio
Level of connectivity	Digital	Density of number of public Wi-Fi hotspots per person	(Hotspot/person)	The wireless technology has revolutionized communication, allowing for various interactive applications. Wireless hotspots, also known as Wi-Fi hotspots, serve as access points that provide network and internet connectivity to mobile devices like laptops and smartphones, typically in public locations which has become an essential technology for the growth and progress of communities.	Indicators linked to proposed metrics from University of Maribor, Maribor (UM)
Level of connectivity	Digital	Percentage of households with access to broadband internet	(%)	The "Broadband Penetration" indicator measures the proportion of households within a specific area (e.g., city, region, or country) that have access to broadband internet services. This metric is expressed as a percentage of the total number of households.	Indicators linked to proposed metrics from University of Maribor, Maribor (UM)
Level of connectivity	Digital	Geographic coverage of broadband and mobile networks	(%)	The indicator measures the geographic area where broadband internet and mobile networks are available. This indicator reflects the physical reach of the infrastructure that provides access to high-speed internet (broadband) and mobile data services. It is typically expressed as a percentage of the total geographic area within a region, city, or country.	Maja et al., 2020
Level of connectivity	Digital	Density of cellphone provider networks reachable in a village	(Number/km ²)	This indicator measures the density of cellphone provider networks in a specific village or rural area. It reflects how many different cellphones network providers are available and accessible per unit of geographic area, typically expressed as number of	Maja et al., 2020

				providers per square kilometer (Number/km ²). This indicator helps understand the availability and competition of mobile services in small or rural communities.	
Level of Digital connectivity	Average monthly downtime of the villages' IT infrastructure	(Hours)		The "IT Infrastructure Downtime" indicator measures the total time during which an organization's IT infrastructure (servers, networks, databases, or other critical components) is unavailable or non-functional. This is usually expressed in hours or minutes over a specific period (e.g., per month or per year).	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators for smart cities
Level of Digital connectivity	Percentage of city area under a white zone/dead spot/not covered by telecommunication connectivity	(%)		This indicator measures the proportion of a villages' geographical area where telecommunication services (such as mobile networks, internet, or landline services) are unavailable or not reliably accessible. These areas are referred to as "white zones" or "dead spots"—zones without any telecommunication signal or coverage. The metric is expressed as a percentage of the total city area.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators for smart cities
Level of Digital connectivity	Average download and upload speeds	(Mbit/s)		The Internet Speed indicator measures the average download and upload speeds that users experience when accessing the internet, expressed in megabits per second (Mbit/s). It reflects the efficiency of a network in transferring data and plays a key role in the quality of online experiences for both personal and business users.	Indicators linked to proposed metrics from University of Maribor, Maribor (UM)
Technical Proficiency of Rural Populations	Normalized Number of STEM Higher Education Degrees per 100,000 Population:	(Total population/Total number of STEM degrees) ×100.000		This indicator measures the number of higher education degrees awarded in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) fields per 100.000 people in a given population. It provides a normalized, absolute count of degrees that allows you to compare across different population sizes. It reflects the proportion of a population that is obtaining advanced qualifications in STEM disciplines, which are crucial for innovation, technological	DigComp Framework; (OECD, 2022)

			advancement, and economic competitiveness.	
Technical Proficiency of Rural Populations	Normalized Number of EIPASS and ICDL Certifications per 100,000 Population	(Total population / Total number of EIPASS and ICDL certifications) ×100,000	This indicator measures the number of EIPASS and ICDL certifications awarded per 100,000 people in a given population. It provides a normalized, absolute count of certifications, enabling comparisons across different population sizes. This metric reflects the level of digital literacy and technical proficiency within the population, which is essential for adapting to the demands of a digital economy and enhancing employability in rural areas	-
Technical Proficiency of Rural Populations	Normalized Number of English Language Certificates (B2 Level) per 100,000 Population:	(Total population / Total number of English language certificates B2 level at least) ×100,000	This indicator measures the number of certificates confirming knowledge of the English language at least at level B2 per 100,000 people in a given population. It provides a normalized count of language proficiency certificates, allowing for comparisons across different population sizes. This metric reflects the population's language skills, which are increasingly important for access to global opportunities, higher education, and international collaboration also in rural areas.	DigComp Framework; (OECD, 2022)

Mobility and Transport: Indicators and metrics

Indicator list

Table 12. Mobility and Transport - Indicators and their prioritization

Dimensions	Sub-dimensions	Indicators	Definitions	Total score	Veto Factor
Mobility and Transport	Technical and information infrastructure	Accessibility and Availability of Public Transportation Services	This indicator measures the extent to which public transport services are available and accessible to rural populations, including frequency, coverage, and proximity of services. It reflects the inclusiveness and usability of the transport network in addressing mobility needs in sparsely populated areas.		
		Level of Digitalization in Public Transport Systems and Infrastructures	Evaluate the extent to which digital technologies are integrated into public transport systems and infrastructures. It assesses features such as the availability of real-time information, digital ticketing systems, automated scheduling, smart traffic management, and integration with digital platforms for mobility-as-a-service (MaaS).		
	Mobility methods and vehicles used for this purpose,	Modal Shift Transport	This indicator measures changes in transportation		

			patterns, specifically the shift from traditional, less sustainable modes (e.g., private car usage) to more sustainable alternatives such as public transport, shared mobility, cycling, or walking.		
		Low-Carbon Fuel Vehicles	This indicator assesses the adoption and use of vehicles powered by low-carbon or renewable fuels, such as electric vehicles (EVs), plug-in hybrids, or vehicles running on biodiesel, in rural areas.		
		Integration of Smart ICT Solutions in Vehicles	This indicator evaluates the adoption of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) solutions in vehicles to enhance functionality, connectivity, and user experience.		
	Legislation.	Adoption of Mobility Regulations and Plans	This indicator evaluates the extent to which rural areas have implemented and enforced mobility regulations and plans that promote sustainable, safe, and efficient transport systems. It reflects the level of institutional commitment to enhancing mobility and transport in rural regions.		

Self-assessment

Before proceeding with the ranking process, participants are encouraged to carefully consider the following questions:

- What is the relative significance of each indicator in achieving the objectives of the selected project?
- How does each specific indicator contribute to the success and long-term sustainability of the project?

Rank each pair of indicators in the pairwise matrix below based on preference, using the scoring system provided. The scale ranges from 1 to 3:

- “One” indicates that the two indicators are equally important;
- “Two” indicates that one indicator is moderately more important than the other;
- “Three” indicates that one indicator is significantly more important than the other.

For each pair of indicators choose a value from 1 to 3. A 3 or 2 to the left column chart shows that the statement on the left is significantly or moderately more important than the one on the right, while a 2 or 3 to the right column chart indicates that the statement on the right is moderately or significantly more important than the one on the left.

Table 13. Mobility and Transport - pairwise matrix

	3	2	1	2	3	
Accessibility and Availability of Public Transportation Services						Level of Digitalization in Public Transport Systems and Infrastructures
Accessibility and Availability of Public Transportation Services						Modal Shift Transport
Accessibility and Availability of Public Transportation Services						Low-Carbon Fuel Vehicles
Accessibility and Availability of Public Transportation Services						Integration of Smart ICT Solutions in Vehicles

Accessibility and Availability of Public Transportation Services						Adoption of Mobility Regulations and Plans
Level of Digitalization in Public Transport Systems and Infrastructures						Modal Shift Transport
Level of Digitalization in Public Transport Systems and Infrastructures						Low-Carbon Fuel Vehicles
Level of Digitalization in Public Transport Systems and Infrastructures						Integration of Smart ICT Solutions in Vehicles
Level of Digitalization in Public Transport Systems and Infrastructures						Adoption of Mobility Regulations and Plans
Modal Shift Transport						Low-Carbon Fuel Vehicles
Modal Shift Transport						Integration of Smart ICT Solutions in Vehicles
Modal Shift Transport						Adoption of Mobility Regulations and Plans
Low-Carbon Fuel Vehicles						Integration of Smart ICT Solutions in Vehicles
Low-Carbon Fuel Vehicles						Adoption of Mobility Regulations

						and Plans
Integration of Smart ICT Solutions in Vehicles						Adoption of Mobility Regulations and Plans

Completing all pairwise comparisons, participants calculate the **total score** for each indicator using “points” across the rows. The values should be added with a positive or negative sign based on the indicator's position in the matrix.

After finalizing the ranking of indicators, reflect on the **essential indicators** that directly impact the project's core objectives and feasibility.

- Any indicator that directly influences the project's success or its ability to meet legal, technical, or environmental requirements should be considered as a **Veto Factor**.
- If any indicator is flagged as a Veto Factor, it must be treated with utmost importance in the decision-making process, even if its ranking in the pairwise comparison is lower than others.
- When completing the ranking and prioritization of indicators, stakeholders should ensure that the Veto Factor is integrated into the final decision.

Metrics, units, importance and sources

Table 14. Mobility and Transport - Metrics and their units

Status indicators	Metric	Units	Importance/Definition	Sources
Accessibility and availability of public transportation services in rural areas	Density of bus stops/shelters in a given area	(Number/km ²)	This indicator measures the density of bus stops or shelters within a specified geographic area, expressed as the number of bus stops or shelters per square kilometer. It provides insight into the accessibility and availability of public transportation services in a given area. A higher density of bus stops indicates better access to public transportation, making it easier for residents to use buses for their daily commutes and travel needs	Kim, J., Park, J., Lee, J., & Jang, K. M. (2024). Examining the socio-spatial patterns of bus shelters with deep learning analysis of street-view images: A case study of 20 cities in the U.S. <i>Cities</i> , 148, 104852. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2024.104852

Accessibility and availability of public transportation services in rural areas	Length of bicycle network (dedicated cycle paths and lanes)	(km)	This indicator measures the length of cycling and walking infrastructure (such as bike lanes, footpaths, and pedestrian walkways) deployed in a specific area, expressed by km	European Commission (A c. Di). (2017). Methodological manual on city statistics: 2017 edition (2017 edition). Publications Office. https://doi.org/10.2785/708009
Accessibility and availability of public transportation services in rural areas	Ratio of cycling and walking infrastructure deployed to population	(km/population)	This indicator measures the length of cycling and walking infrastructure (such as bike lanes, footpaths, and pedestrian walkways) deployed in a specific area, expressed as a ratio to the number of population in that area. It helps assess the availability and accessibility of active transportation options relative to the population density.	European Commission (A c. Di). (2017). Methodological manual on city statistics: 2017 edition (2017 edition). Publications Office. https://doi.org/10.2785/708009
Accessibility and availability of public transportation services in rural areas	Percentage of the villages public transport network covered by a unified payment system	(%)	For rural areas, a high percentage of the public transport network covered by a unified payment system is key to simplifying access, encouraging the use of public transport, and improving convenience for residents and visitors, particularly in areas where transport options are fragmented.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Accessibility and availability of public transportation services in rural areas	Percentage of municipal budget allocated for provision of mobility aids, devices, and assistive technologies to citizens with special needs	(%)	This metric measures the share of a municipality's budget dedicated to providing mobility aids, devices, and assistive technologies that support citizens with special needs. It includes funding for essential resources such as wheelchairs, hearing aids, visual assistance tools, and other accessibility devices that help improve mobility, autonomy, and quality	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators

			of life for residents with disabilities.	
Adoption of Mobility Regulations and Plans	Number of villages with active Sustainable Mobility Plans (SMPs) or similar plans tailored for rural areas, divided by the total number of villages in the area	Percentage (%)	This metric represents the proportion of rural villages that have adopted and are actively implementing mobility plans focused on sustainable transportation. These plans might include provisions for public transport, active mobility (cycling and walking), and low-emission vehicles, tailored to rural needs.	
Adoption of Mobility Regulations and Plans	Percentage of rural villages with zoning laws supporting mobility infrastructure	Percentage (%)	This metric measures the share of rural villages that have enacted zoning regulations to prioritize and support the development of mobility infrastructure, such as bike lanes, public transport hubs, and electric vehicle charging stations.	
Adoption of Mobility Regulations and Plans	Number of rural villages that have introduced speed limits, traffic-calming measures, or other road safety initiatives, divided by the total number of villages	% of communities	This metric reflects the proportion of rural villages actively implementing road safety measures. These initiatives may include reduced speed zones, installation of speed bumps, or pedestrian-friendly infrastructure.	
Integration of Smart Solutions in collective service vehicles	Number of trains operating per hour that provide smart services for passengers.	Number of Smart Service Trains per Hour= Operating Hours per Day/Total Smart Service Trains in Operation per Day x 100	This metric measures the availability and frequency of trains equipped with modern, passenger-friendly smart services such as Wi-Fi, USB charging ports, and standard power outlets. It reflects advancements in rail transport infrastructure aimed at improving the quality of service and enhancing the travel experience for passengers in both rural and regional contexts.	Dotter, F., Lennert, F., & Patatouka, E. (2019). Smart Mobility Systems and Services.

Integration of Smart Solutions in collective service vehicles	Number of Private Collective Transport Buses Offering Smart Services	Smart Service Buses Per Day= Total Operated Buses Per Day/Total Smart Service Buses in Operation (Daily) x100	This metric measures the availability of smart services such as Wi-Fi, USB charging ports, and standard power outlets, in private collective transport buses used in rural and regional areas. It focuses on enhancing passenger experience and providing digital connectivity for private collective travel options.	Dotter, F., Lennert, F., & Patatouka, E. (2019). Smart Mobility Systems and Services.
Integration of Smart Solutions in collective service vehicles	Number of Public Transport Buses Offering Smart Services	Smart Service Buses Per Day= Total Operated Buses Per Day/Total Smart Service Buses in Operation (Daily) x100	This metric evaluates the penetration of smart services such as Wi-Fi, USB charging ports, and standard power outlets, in public bus transport, emphasizing the role of public authorities in advancing accessible and modern mobility solutions in rural and urban fringe areas.	Dotter, F., Lennert, F., & Patatouka, E. (2019). Smart Mobility Systems and Services.
Level of Digitalization in Public Transport Systems and infrastructures in Rural Communities	Percentage of public transport lines equipped with a real-time system	(%)	For rural areas, having a high percentage of public transport lines equipped with real-time systems is critical to making transport services more reliable, accessible, and efficient, especially in contexts where public transportation options are limited and services tend to be infrequent.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Level of Digitalization in Public Transport Systems and infrastructures in Rural Communities	Percentage of public transport routes with municipally provided and/or managed internet connectivity for commuters	(%)	For rural areas, a high percentage of public transport routes with internet connectivity is essential to improving commuter experience, enhancing digital inclusion, and promoting the use of public transportation, particularly where connectivity options are limited.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Level of digitalization in Public Transport Systems and infrastructures in Rural Communities	Percentage of marked pedestrian crosswalks equipped with accessible pedestrian signals	(%)	In rural areas, a high percentage of crosswalks equipped with accessible pedestrian signals is	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators

			crucial for improving pedestrian safety, ensuring accessibility for all, and enhancing the overall walkability and inclusivity of the community. This is especially important in areas with aging populations, fewer transport options, and less pedestrian infrastructure.	
Level of Digitalization in Public Transport Systems and infrastructures in Rural Communities	Percentage of outdoor lamp posts and street lighting that are managed by a light management system	(%)	In rural areas, outdoor lighting is often less concentrated than in urban settings, leading to darker environments at night, which can pose safety risks. The percentage of outdoor lamp posts and street lighting that are managed by a light management system indicator helps assess the efficacy and efficiency of street lighting systems. Smart lamp posts can improve safety by adjusting brightness based on real-time conditions, such as the presence of pedestrians or vehicles, while also conserving energy and reducing light pollution. This metric provides valuable insights into how effectively rural areas are balancing safety with energy efficiency in their public lighting infrastructure.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Level of Digitalization in Public Transport Systems and infrastructures in Rural Communities	Percentage of street lighting that has been refurbished	(%)	Upgrading older streetlights improves the quality of lighting, increasing visibility for pedestrians and drivers. This is especially important in rural areas, where roads and pathways may be poorly lit, and improved lighting can reduce the risk of accidents and enhance night-time safety.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators

Level of Digitalization in Public Transport Systems and infrastructures in Rural Communities	Percentage of Public Parking Spaces Equipped with both E-payment Systems and traditional option	(%)	In rural areas, where digital infrastructure may not be as robust, offering both e-payment and traditional options ensures inclusivity for residents who may not have access to digital payment methods, while still encouraging modernization	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Level of Digitalization in Public Transport Systems and infrastructures in Rural Communities	Number of Electric Charging Stations per Electric Vehicle (EV)	(Number)	In rural areas, tracking the number of electric charging stations per EV is essential for ensuring that charging infrastructure is developed at a pace that meets current and future demand. This metric promotes convenience, economic development, and sustainability.	EAFO database https://alternative-fuels-observatory.ec.europa.eu/
Level of Digitalization in Public Transport Systems and infrastructures in Rural Communities	Percentage of the total regional railway network powered by electricity.	Percentage (%)	This metric measures the proportion of the railway network in a specific region that operates using electric power instead of diesel or other fossil fuels. It is calculated by comparing the total length of electrified railway lines to the total length of the regional railway network.	EAFO database https://alternative-fuels-observatory.ec.europa.eu/
Low-carbon Fuels Veicles	Number of Registered Electric Vehicles per 100 000 population	Electric Vehicles per 100,000 inhabitants	This metric measures the penetration of electric mobility in rural communities, highlighting the adoption of sustainable transport and machinery solutions across various sectors. The metric encompasses multiple categories of vehicles serving diverse rural functions: Passenger Cars for personal and business use; Trucks for goods transport and logistics; Tractors and other farm machinery essential for agricultural operations; Specialized Vehicles utilized in	Indicators linked to proposed metrics from University of Maribor, Maribor (UM)

				forestry, fisheries, and other rural industries.	
Low-carbon Vehicles	Fuels	Percentage of Electric Vehicles	Percentage (%)	This metric reflects the shift toward low-emission technology across the rural economy, emphasizing how electric and hybrid vehicles support the functional needs of these areas.	Indicators linked to proposed metrics from University of Maribor, Maribor (UM)
Low-carbon Vehicles	Fuels	Share of alternative fuelled Heavy-Duty class vehicles	Percentage (%)	This metric evaluates the proportion of Heavy-Duty class vehicles (e.g., trucks, buses, agricultural vehicles) powered by renewable energy sources in rural areas. It includes vehicles running on electricity produced from renewable sources (e.g., solar or wind-powered grids) and those using biofuels like biodiesel.	EAFO database https://alternative-fuels-observatory.ec.europa.eu/
Low-carbon Vehicles	Fuels	Share of alternative fuelled light-duty (M1 + N1) vehicles	(Number)	This metric evaluates the proportion of light-duty vehicles (e.g., cars, mini buses) powered by alternative energy sources in rural areas. It includes vehicles running on electricity produced from renewable sources (e.g., solar or wind-powered grids) and those using biofuels like biodiesel.	EAFO database https://alternative-fuels-observatory.ec.europa.eu/
Modal Shift Transport		Number of bicycles available through municipally provided bicycle sharing services per 100 000 population	(Number)	The metric measures sustainable, affordable, and healthy transportation options, enhances local accessibility, and supports tourism and economic development.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Modal Shift Transport		Number cars in car sharing schemes per 100.000 populations	(Number)	Rural areas are often highly car-dependent, as public transportation systems typically face low ridership and limited coverage. This metric helps track the	Circularity Metrics Lab. (2024, luglio 16). Number cars in car sharing schemes. European Environment Agency. https://www.eea.europ

			availability of affordable, flexible, and sustainable transportation options, enabling rural communities to meet modern mobility needs while addressing the unique challenges of low population density and long distances between essential services.	a.eu/en/circularity/thematic-metrics/consumer/number-cars-in-car-sharing-schemes-1
Modal Shift Transport	Number of Buses per 1000 People	(Number)	This metric quantifies the availability of bus services in a rural area, normalized per 1000 residents. It reflects the accessibility of public transport and is a proxy for evaluating how well rural communities are served by buses.	Public – Private Infrastructure Advisory Facility (PPIAF). (2006.). Benchmarks and Indicators. Urban Bus Toolkit. Last view November, 26 2024, https://www.ppiaf.org/sites/ppiaf.org/files/documents/toolkits/UrbanBusToolkit/assets/1/1c/1c.html
Modal Shift Transport	Number Trains per 10,000 Population	(Number)	This metric measures the frequency of train services available to rural residents, normalized per 10,000 population. It captures the role of rail transport in providing long-distance and regional connectivity.	
Modal Shift Transport	Cost of a combined monthly ticket (all modes of public transport) in the rural area	Currency value per month (e.g., euros/month).	This metric measures the total price of a monthly ticket that provides access to all available modes of public transport within a rural area. Modes may include buses, trains, trams, or other forms of shared mobility where applicable.	European Commission (A c. Di). (2017). Methodological manual on city statistics: 2017 edition (2017 edition). Publications Office. https://doi.org/10.2785/708009

Economy: Indicators and metrics

Indicator list

Table 15. Economy - Indicators and their prioritization

Dimensions	Sub-dimensions	Indicators	Definitions	Total score	Veto Factor
Economy	Primary Sector	Status of Precision Agriculture Technologies	Measures the adoption of precision tools that optimize resource use and improve yield.		
		Level of Digitization and Automation in Agricultural Systems	Evaluates the integration of digital and automated processes in farm management.		
		Presence of Circular Agricultural Practices	Assesses the implementation of sustainable practices, such as waste reduction and resource recycling.		
		Level of Investment in Innovative Agriculture	Indicates the extent of financial resources directed toward modernizing agricultural methods.		
	Secondary Sector	Level of Decentralization in Electricity Production	Measures the spread of localized energy generation facilities, enhancing local energy resilience.		
		Adoption of Circular Energy Solutions	Evaluates practices like energy recycling and renewable		

			energy usage to reduce waste.		
		Level of Digitalization in the Energy Sector	Assesses the integration of digital tools in managing and optimizing energy resources.		
		Energy Storage Capacity	Measures the storage capabilities for renewable energy, supporting energy availability and reliability.		
	Tertiary Sector / Advanced Tertiary Sector:	Level of Technical ICT Skills in the Labor Force	Evaluates the prevalence of ICT skills within the local workforce, supporting digital economy initiatives.		
		Accessibility of Cultural and Recreational Initiatives	This indicator measures the ease with which residents and visitors in rural communities can access cultural and recreational activities including events, facilities, and programs.		
		Economic Investment in ICT Sectors	Indicates the level of financial commitment to ICT industries, driving innovation and employment in rural areas.		

Self-assessment

Before proceeding with the ranking process, participants are encouraged to carefully consider the following questions:

- What is the relative significance of each indicator in achieving the objectives of the selected project?
- How does each specific indicator contribute to the success and long-term sustainability of the project?

Rank each pair of indicators in the pairwise matrix below based on preference, using the scoring system provided. The scale ranges from 1 to 3:

- “One” indicates that the two indicators are equally important;
- “Two” indicates that one indicator is moderately more important than the other;
- “Three” indicates that one indicator is significantly more important than the other.

For each pair of indicators choose a value from 1 to 3. A 3 or 2 to the left column chart shows that the statement on the left is significantly or moderately more important than the one on the right, while a 2 or 3 to the right column chart indicates that the statement on the right is moderately or significantly more important than the one on the left.

Table 16. Economy - pairwise matrix

	3	2	1	2	3	
Status of Precision Agriculture Technologies						Level of Digitization and Automation in Agricultural Systems
Status of Precision Agriculture Technologies						Presence of Circular Agricultural Practices
Status of Precision Agriculture Technologies						Level of Investment in Innovative Agriculture
Status of Precision Agriculture Technologies						Level of Decentralization in Electricity Production
Status of Precision Agriculture Technologies						Adoption of Circular Energy Solutions

Status of Precision Agriculture Technologies						Level of Digitalization in the Energy Sector
Status of Precision Agriculture Technologies						Energy Storage Capacity
Status of Precision Agriculture Technologies						Level of Technical ICT Skills in the Labor Force
Status of Precision Agriculture Technologies						Accessibility of Cultural and Recreational Initiatives
Status of Precision Agriculture Technologies						Economic Investment in ICT Sectors
Level of Digitization and Automation in Agricultural Systems						Presence of Circular Agricultural Practices
Level of Digitization and Automation in Agricultural Systems						Level of Investment in Innovative Agriculture
Level of Digitization and Automation in Agricultural Systems						Level of Decentralization in Electricity Production
Level of Digitization and Automation in Agricultural Systems						Adoption of Circular Energy Solutions
Level of Digitization and Automation in Agricultural Systems						Level of Digitalization in the Energy Sector

Level of Digitization and Automation in Agricultural Systems							Energy Storage Capacity
Level of Digitization and Automation in Agricultural Systems							Level of Technical ICT Skills in the Labor Force
Level of Digitization and Automation in Agricultural Systems							Accessibility of Cultural and Recreational Initiatives
Level of Digitization and Automation in Agricultural Systems							Economic Investment in ICT Sectors
Presence of Circular Agricultural Practices							Level of Investment in Innovative Agriculture
Presence of Circular Agricultural Practices							Level of Decentralization in Electricity Production
Presence of Circular Agricultural Practices							Adoption of Circular Energy Solutions
Presence of Circular Agricultural Practices							Level of Digitalization in the Energy Sector
Presence of Circular Agricultural Practices							Energy Storage Capacity
Presence of Circular Agricultural Practices							Level of Technical ICT Skills in the Labor Force
Presence of Circular Agricultural Practices							Accessibility of Cultural and Recreational Initiatives

Presence of Circular Agricultural Practices							Economic Investment in ICT Sectors
Level of Investment in Innovative Agriculture							Level of Decentralization in Electricity Production
Level of Investment in Innovative Agriculture							Adoption of Circular Energy Solutions
Level of Investment in Innovative Agriculture							Level of Digitalization in the Energy Sector
Level of Investment in Innovative Agriculture							Energy Storage Capacity
Level of Investment in Innovative Agriculture							Level of Technical ICT Skills in the Labor Force
Level of Investment in Innovative Agriculture							Accessibility of Cultural and Recreational Initiatives
Level of Investment in Innovative Agriculture							Economic Investment in ICT Sectors
Level of Decentralization in Electricity Production							Adoption of Circular Energy Solutions
Level of Decentralization in Electricity Production							Level of Digitalization in the Energy Sector
Level of Decentralization in Electricity Production							Energy Storage Capacity
Level of Decentralization in Electricity Production							Level of Technical ICT Skills in the Labor Force
Level of Decentralization							Accessibility of Cultural and

n in Electricity Production						Recreational Initiatives
Level of Decentralization in Electricity Production						Economic Investment in ICT Sectors
Adoption of Circular Energy Solutions						Level of Digitalization in the Energy Sector
Adoption of Circular Energy Solutions						Energy Storage Capacity
Adoption of Circular Energy Solutions						Level of Technical ICT Skills in the Labor Force
Adoption of Circular Energy Solutions						Accessibility of Cultural and Recreational Initiatives
Adoption of Circular Energy Solutions						Economic Investment in ICT Sectors
Level of Digitalization in the Energy Sector						Energy Storage Capacity
Level of Digitalization in the Energy Sector						Level of Technical ICT Skills in the Labor Force
Level of Digitalization in the Energy Sector						Accessibility of Cultural and Recreational Initiatives
Level of Digitalization in the Energy Sector						Economic Investment in ICT Sectors
Energy Storage Capacity						Level of Technical ICT Skills in the Labor Force

Energy Storage Capacity						Accessibility of Cultural and Recreational Initiatives
Energy Storage Capacity						Economic Investment in ICT Sectors
Level of Technical ICT Skills in the Labor Force						Accessibility of Cultural and Recreational Initiatives
Level of Technical ICT Skills in the Labor Force						Economic Investment in ICT Sectors
Accessibility of Cultural and Recreational Initiatives						Economic Investment in ICT Sectors

Completing all pairwise comparisons, participants calculate the **total score** for each indicator using “points” across the rows. The values should be added with a positive or negative sign based on the indicator's position in the matrix.

After finalizing the ranking of indicators, reflect on the **essential indicators** that directly impact the project's core objectives and feasibility.

- Any indicator that directly influences the project's success or its ability to meet legal, technical, or environmental requirements should be considered as a **Veto Factor**.
- If any indicator is flagged as a Veto Factor, it must be treated with utmost importance in the decision-making process, even if its ranking in the pairwise comparison is lower than others.
- When completing the ranking and prioritization of indicators, stakeholders should ensure that the Veto Factor is integrated into the final decision.

Metrics, units, importance and sources

Table 17. Economy - Metrics and their units

Status indicators	Metric	Units	Importance/Definition	Sources
Accessibility of Cultural and Recreational Initiatives	Percentage of recreation services that can be booked online	%	This metric measures the percentage of recreation services (such as sports facilities, cultural events, community activities, or social programs) that offer online booking options. These services are designed to promote physical, cultural, and social development within a community. In rural areas, where physical access to services can be limited due to distance, the ability to book recreation services online makes these activities more accessible to a wider population..	
Accessibility of Cultural and Recreational initiatives	Number of Smart Tourism Initiatives (such as Virtual Tours, Podcasts, QR Codes, GPS Tracking Technology, and Gamification)	(Number and category)	This metric tracks the number of smart tourism initiatives implemented in a given area. These initiatives include virtual tours, podcasts, QR codes, GPS tracking technology, and gamification elements that enhance the tourism experience through digital innovations.	
Accessibility of Cultural and Recreational Services	Volume of Economic Investment in Digital Marketing in the Tourism Sector as a Percentage of Total Marketing Investment (%)	(%)	This metric measures the proportion of total marketing investment that is allocated specifically to digital marketing within the tourism sector. It provides insight into how much focus is placed on digital strategies compared to traditional marketing approaches. A higher proportion of investment in digital marketing suggests	

			that rural tourism operators are leveraging modern tools to promote destinations more efficiently and effectively.	
Accessibility of Cultural and Recreational Services	Percentage of the community cultural records that have been digitized	(%)	This metric measures the proportion of cultural records—including archives, historical documents, photos, and other forms of cultural heritage—that have been digitized. It reflects the extent to which a community has taken steps to preserve and make accessible its cultural heritage in a digital format.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Accessibility of Cultural and Recreational Services	Proportion of cultural institutions and events in the villages for which online participation is offered.	%	The metric measures the proportion of cultural institutions and events for which online participation is offered. Cultural resources online include: events and activities provided online, and watched or listened through electric/virtual media.	ITU 4902, ITU 4903
Accessibility of Cultural and Recreational Services	Number of public library book and e-book titles per 100.000 population	(Number)	This metric measures the number of book and e-book titles available in public libraries for every 100.000 people in a given community. It provides insight into the availability and diversity of reading materials that are accessible to the public, both in physical and digital formats.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Adoption of Circular Energy Solutions	Electrical and thermal energy (kWh) produced from waste water treatment, solid waste treatment and other waste heat resources, as part of the villages' energy mix (%)	(%)	This metric shows how well rural areas are utilizing waste resources (e.g., wastewater, solid waste, and other waste heat) to produce renewable energy. They promote sustainability, energy independence, and cost-efficiency, all of which are essential in	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators

			rural settings where resources are often scarce and access to centralized energy infrastructure can be limited.	
Adoption of Circular Energy Solutions	Electrical and thermal energy produced from wastewater treatment per capita per year	(kWh)	This metric shows how well rural areas are utilizing waste resources (e.g., wastewater, solid waste, and other waste heat) to produce renewable energy. They promote sustainability, energy independence, and cost-efficiency, all of which are essential in rural settings where resources are often scarce and access to centralized energy infrastructure can be limited.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Adoption of Circular Energy Solutions	Electrical and thermal energy produced from solid waste treatment per capita per year	(kWh)	This metric shows how well rural areas are utilizing waste resources (e.g., wastewater, solid waste, and other waste heat) to produce renewable energy. They promote sustainability, energy independence, and cost-efficiency, all of which are essential in rural settings where resources are often scarce and access to centralized energy infrastructure can be limited.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Adoption of Circular Energy Solutions	Percentage of Public Buildings Requiring Renovation/Refurbishment by Floor Area	Square meters	This metric measures the percentage of total floor area of public buildings in rural areas that require renovation or refurbishment. It helps assess the physical condition of public infrastructure and the need for upgrades or maintenance to improve safety, energy efficiency, and functionality.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators

Economic Investment in ICT Sectors	Number and volume of financial products designed for digital transformation	(Number, €)	This indicator measures both the quantity (number) and the size (volume) of financial products that are specifically aimed at supporting digital transformation initiatives in a given region or sector. These financial products can include loans, grants, subsidies, or investment schemes that help businesses or public entities adopt digital technologies. This metric captures the financial readiness of rural areas to embrace digital transformation.	
Economic Investment in ICT Sectors	Externally funded digital projects e.g., EU grants, national funds, etc	(Number)	This metric measures the number and total funding volume of digital projects in a region or community that receive financial support from external sources, such as EU grants, national funds, or international development organizations. It reflects the degree to which local initiatives are leveraging external funding to promote digital transformation and innovation.	
Energy Capacity Storage	Percentage of Households/buildings with energy storage systems	(%)	This metric measures the percentage of households and buildings in a community that are equipped with energy storage systems (ESS). These systems can include technologies such as batteries (e.g., lithium-ion batteries, lead-acid batteries) or other forms of energy storage that allow for the storage of electricity for later use.	
Energy Capacity Storage	Storage Capacity of the Community Energy Grid per Capita	(GJ/person)	This metric measures the energy storage capacity (in gigajoules, GJ) of a community	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators

			energy grid per person in rural areas. It reflects the community's ability to store surplus energy generated from local sources, such as solar or wind power, and use it when demand is higher or renewable generation is lower (e.g., at night or during low-wind conditions).	
Level of Decentralization in Electricity Production	Households/buildings with small-scale decentralized electricity production systems	(%, number and types)	This metric focuses on penetration rates, making it useful for tracking how well rural areas are embracing decentralized energy solutions, such as solar panels, wind turbines, or bioenergy systems.	
Level of Decentralization in Electricity Production	Annual Energy Produced from decentralized electricity production systems in Villages as percentage of total energy consumption	(%, kWh)	This metric reflects the degree of energy self-sufficiency in rural areas, where renewable energy can provide local, decentralized power sources that reduce reliance on external energy grids.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Level of Digitalization in the Energy Sector	Percentage of Households/Buildings Connected to a Smart Grid System	(%)	This metric for rural areas, reflect the community's ability to manage energy more efficiently, integrate renewable sources, and improve reliability. It also facilitates the transition to a more modern and sustainable energy landscape, ensuring that rural areas can thrive in an increasingly energy-conscious world.	
Level of Digitalization in the Energy Sector	Households and organizations involved in energy communities	(%)	Rural areas often face challenges related to energy access and dependence on external suppliers. Energy communities, where households and organizations collectively produce, share, or manage energy (often from renewable sources),	

			can foster local energy autonomy. This metric is highly relevant in rural settings because it reflects a community's move toward sustainable energy, local collaboration, and resilience.	
Level of Digitalization in the Energy Sector	Percentage of households with smart electricity meters	(%)	This metric directly targets households, which are often the main consumers of electricity in rural areas. It tracks the adoption of smart metering at the individual level, providing insight into energy efficiency and consumer behavior.	
Level of Digitalization in the Energy Sector	Percentage of public buildings in the village equipped with smart energy meters	(%)	This metric measures the proportion of public buildings (such as schools, hospitals, municipal offices, and community centers) in a village that are equipped with smart energy meters. Smart meters provide real-time data on energy consumption, enabling better energy management and efficiency.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Level of Digitization and Automation in Agricultural Systems	Percentage of Agricultural Firms Using Digital Platforms for Information and Market Access	(%)	The Percentage of Agricultural Firms Using Digital Platforms for Information and Market Access measures the extent to which agricultural businesses are adopting digital tools to access crucial data—such as weather forecasts, crop management tips, and best practices—as well as to connect directly with buyers and suppliers.	
Level of Digitization and Automation in Agricultural Systems	Percentage of total agricultural trade conducted via digital platforms	(%)	The metric offers insights into the economic impact of these digital tools. By tracking how much agricultural trade occurs through online	

			platforms, this indicator shows the sector's shift towards e-commerce, which simplifies access to larger markets, improves pricing fairness, and reduces reliance on traditional intermediaries.	
Level of Digitization and Automation in Agricultural Systems	Percentage of Livestock Firms Utilizing Automated Systems for Dairy, Cleaning, and Feeding	(%)	This metric measures the percentage of livestock firms that have implemented automated systems in critical areas like dairy operations, cleaning processes, and feeding systems, offering a comprehensive view of how automation is reshaping livestock management. By consolidating these key functions into a single metric, the indicator provides a clearer picture of the scale and depth of technological adoption in the livestock sector.	
Level of Investment in Innovative Agriculture	Annual percentage of regional budget spent on innovative agriculture initiatives	(%)	This metric measures the proportion of the regional budget that is dedicated to supporting innovative agricultural initiatives, such as research and development, sustainable practices, technology adoption, and training programs. It reflects the municipality's commitment to fostering a progressive agricultural sector that is responsive to modern challenges.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Level of Technical ICT Skills in the Labor Force	Percentage of labour force employed in occupations in the Information and Communications Technology (ICT) sector	(%)	The Percentage of Labor Force Employed in ICT reflects the region's ability to attract new industries, retain skilled workers, and foster innovation and digital transformation, which are key to ensuring sustainable and resilient	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators

			development in rural communities.	
Level of Technical ICT Skills in the Labor Force	Percentage of the labour force employed in occupations in the Education and Research & Development sectors	(%)	The Percentage of Labor Force Employed in Education and R&D reflects the region's ability to attract new industries, retain skilled workers, and foster innovation and digital transformation, which are key to ensuring sustainable and resilient development in rural communities.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Level of Technical ICT Skills in the Labor Force	Proportion of e-service companies with core business related to GIS serving the public and private sector	% of companies	GIS services enable better spatial analysis and visualization, supporting informed decision-making for urban planning, environmental management, and public health. This indicator measures the percentage of e-service companies that primarily focus on GIS technologies and provide services public entities, private companies, and other organizations.	ITU 4901
Level of Technical ICT Skills in the Labor Force	Proportion of companies which provide network-based services (including e-commerce, e-learning, e-entertainment, cloud computing etc.).	% of companies	Number of registered companies providing online serviced (including e-commerce, e-learning, e-entertainment, cloud computing, etc.).	ITU 4901
Level of Technical ICT Skills in the Labor Force	Proportion of e-service companies with core business related to big data storage and analysis serving Public and Private Sectors	% of companies	This metric measures the percentage of e-service companies whose primary focus is on big data storage and analytical services, catering to public entities, private businesses, and other organizations.	ITU 4901
Presence of Circular Agricultural Practices	Annual total collected municipal food waste sent to a processing facility for composting per capita	(Number in tonnes)	This metric measures the annual total of municipal food waste collected and sent to processing facilities for composting,	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators

			normalized by the population size. It reflects the effectiveness of municipal waste management systems in diverting food waste from landfills.	
Presence of Circular Agricultural Practices	Annual Agricultural Waste Collected for Composting per Hectare	(kg)	This metric measures the annual total of agricultural waste collected and sent to processing facilities for composting, normalized by the hectare of agricultural land. It reflects the effectiveness of waste management practices within the agricultural sector and highlights the potential for resource recovery.	
Presence of Circular Agricultural Practices	Percentage of the villages' solid waste that is biologically treated and used as compost or biogas % in tonnes	(%)	This metric measures the percentage of household waste collected and sent to processing facilities for composting or used to reate biogas. It reflects the effectiveness of waste management practices within the agricultural sector and highlights the potential for resource recovery	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Status of Precision Agriculture Technologies	Percentage of total farmland managed with precision agriculture technologies	(%)	Precision agriculture technologies (PAT) optimize the use of agricultural inputs (e.g., fertilizers, fuel) by accounting for the spatial and temporal variability of the field. The metric allows for the assessment of how extensively these advanced tools are being adopted across agricultural operations.	
Status of Precision Agriculture Technologies	Number of firms adopted precision agriculture technologies per 1,000 Agricultural Firms (Number)	(Number)	Precision agriculture technologies (PAT) optimize the use of agricultural inputs (e.g., fertilizers, fuel) by accounting for the spatial and temporal variability of the field.	

			By tracking this metric, policymakers and stakeholders can gauge the level of technological advancement in agriculture and its role in driving economic growth and rural development.	
Status of Precision Agriculture Technologies	Percentage of total farmland products produced using Soilless Agricultural Production Systems	(%)	This metric tracks the adoption of soilless agricultural systems, such as hydroponics, aeroponics, or aquaponics, in relation to the firms' productivity and number of agricultural firms. Percentage and Normalizing help to understand the penetration rate of these innovative farming techniques within the agricultural sector.	
Status of Precision Agriculture Technologies	Number of Soilless Agricultural Production Systems per 1,000 Agricultural Firms (Number)	(Number)	This metric tracks the adoption of soilless agricultural systems, such as hydroponics, aeroponics, or aquaponics, in relation to the firm's productivity and number of agricultural firms. Percentage and Normalizing help to understand the penetration rate of these innovative farming techniques within the agricultural sector.	
Status of Precision Agriculture Technologies	Percentage of Rural Agricultural Land Using Smart Irrigation Systems	(%)	This metric measures the proportion of agricultural land in rural areas that has adopted smart irrigation technologies, such as drip irrigation, soil moisture sensors, and automated watering systems	

Governance and Policy: Indicators and metrics

Indicator list

Table 18. Governance and Policy - Indicators and their prioritization

Dimensions	Sub-dimensions	Indicators	Definitions	Total score	Veto Factor
Governance and Policy	Public Governance	Existence of Strategies, Rules, and Regulations to Promote ICT Literacy	Assesses the presence of formal policies, strategies, and regulations aimed at improving ICT literacy among citizens to enable digital inclusion and smart governance practices.		
		Level of Information and Data Availability and Accessibility	Measures the extent to which community members have access to accurate, relevant, and up-to-date information and data for decision-making and participation in governance.		
		Level of Online Service Accessibility	Evaluates the availability and usability of online public services for citizens and businesses.		
		Level of Investment in Smart Transition Initiatives	Tracks the financial resources allocated by governments to projects and programs that drive smart development in rural communities.		
	Non-Governmental Support	Level of Information and Data Availability and Accessibility	Assesses how non-governmental actors (e.g., NGOs, private		

			organizations) contribute to providing relevant data and resources to the community.		
		Level of Civil Society Involvement and Engagement in Policy Processes	Measures the degree to which civil society organizations and citizens participate in policy-making and implementation processes.		
		Level of Investment in Smart Transition Initiatives	Evaluates financial contributions from non-governmental actors to projects advancing smart rural development.		
	Policy Development and Implementation	Level of Civil Society Involvement and Engagement in Policy Processes	Tracks the participation of civil society in shaping and executing policies at the local level.		
		Level of Intersectionality in Rural Governance Practices	Measures the extent to which governance practices integrate diverse demographic, social, and economic perspectives to ensure equity and inclusion.		

Self-assessment

Before proceeding with the ranking process, participants are encouraged to carefully consider the following questions:

- What is the relative significance of each indicator in achieving the objectives of the selected project?
- How does each specific indicator contribute to the success and long-term sustainability of the project?

Rank each pair of indicators in the pairwise matrix below based on preference, using the scoring system provided. The scale ranges from 1 to 3:

- “One” indicates that the two indicators are equally important;
- “Two” indicates that one indicator is moderately more important than the other;
- “Three” indicates that one indicator is significantly more important than the other.

For each pair of indicators choose a value from 1 to 3. A 3 or 2 to the left column chart shows that the statement on the left is significantly or moderately more important than the one on the right, while a 2 or 3 to the right column chart indicates that the statement on the right is moderately or significantly more important than the one on the left.

Table 19. Governance and Policy - pairwise matrix

	3	2	1	2	3	
Existence of Strategies, Rules, and Regulations to Promote ICT Literacy						Level of Information and Data Availability and Accessibility
Existence of Strategies, Rules, and Regulations to Promote ICT Literacy						Level of Online Service Accessibility
Existence of Strategies, Rules, and Regulations to Promote ICT Literacy						Level of Investment in Smart Transition Initiatives
Existence of Strategies, Rules, and Regulations to Promote ICT Literacy						Level of Civil Society Involvement and Engagement in Policy Processes
Existence of Strategies, Rules, and Regulations to Promote ICT Literacy						Level of Intersectionality in Rural Governance Practices
Level of Information and Data						Level of Online Service Accessibility

Availability and Accessibility						
Level of Information and Data Availability and Accessibility						Level of Investment in Smart Transition Initiatives
Level of Information and Data Availability and Accessibility						Level of Civil Society Involvement and Engagement in Policy Processes
Level of Information and Data Availability and Accessibility						Level of Intersectionality in Rural Governance Practices
Level of Online Service Accessibility						Level of Investment in Smart Transition Initiatives
Level of Online Service Accessibility						Level of Civil Society Involvement and Engagement in Policy Processes
Level of Online Service Accessibility						Level of Intersectionality in Rural Governance Practices
Level of Investment in Smart Transition Initiatives						Level of Civil Society Involvement and Engagement in Policy Processes
Level of Investment in Smart Transition Initiatives						Level of Intersectionality in Rural Governance Practices
Level of Investment in Smart Transition Initiatives						Level of Intersectionality in Rural Governance Practices

Completing all pairwise comparisons, participants calculate the **total score** for each indicator using “points” across the rows. The values should be added with a positive or negative sign based on the indicator's position in the matrix.

After finalizing the ranking of indicators, reflect on the **essential indicators** that directly impact the project's core objectives and feasibility.

- Any indicator that directly influences the project's success or its ability to meet legal, technical, or environmental requirements should be considered as a **Veto Factor**.
- If any indicator is flagged as a Veto Factor, it must be treated with utmost importance in the decision-making process, even if its ranking in the pairwise comparison is lower than others.
- When completing the ranking and prioritization of indicators, stakeholders should ensure that the Veto Factor is integrated into the final decision.

Metrics, units, importance and sources

Table 20. Governance and Policy - Metrics and their units

Status indicators	Metric	Units	Importance/Definition	Sources
Existence of strategies, rules and regulations to enable ICT literacy among inhabitants	Number of strategies, rules and regulations to enable ICT literacy among inhabitants	Number	The metric measures the presence of strategies, regulations, voluntary work or interest organizations to enhance ICT literacy among all city inhabitants. This includes mechanisms that enable public knowledge and skill development.	ITU 4901
Level of civil society involvement and engagement in policy processes.	Number of collaborative digital and rural development projects with civil society organizations (CSOs)	(Number)	This metric captures the extent of partnerships between local authorities or communities and CSOs aimed at advancing digital inclusion and sustainable rural development. A higher number of collaborations reflects a well-engaged civil society and a collaborative approach to rural digital transformation, which is essential for addressing unique rural needs.	

Level of civil society involvement and engagement in policy processes.	Percentage of digital policies developed with public consultation and community input	(%)	This metric reflects the proportion of digital policies that actively incorporate insights and feedback from community members and stakeholders. A higher percentage of policies with community input suggests an inclusive approach, ensuring that digital development aligns with the expectations and challenges of rural residents.	
Level of Information and Data Availability and Accessibility	Percentage of local government datasets available to the public (%)	(%)	This metric measures the degree of openness and transparency in municipal data-sharing practices by focusing on the proportion of all datasets collected, maintained, or produced by village governments that are accessible to the public through online platforms or other open data channels.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators; ITU 4903
Level of Information and Data Availability and Accessibility	Average response time to relevant inquiries made through the villages' non-emergency inquiry system	(Time)	This metric calculates the average duration (in days) taken by the village public servants to respond to non-urgent questions or service requests from residents. It typically includes inquiries related to information requests, community updates, service information, and other non-emergency needs. It measures the efficiency of local government or community systems in responding to non-emergency inquiries from residents.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Level of Information and Data Availability and Accessibility	Percentage of local businesses contracted to provide community services that have data openly available	(%)	This metric measures the percentage of local businesses that are contracted to provide community services (e.g., waste management, transportation, maintenance, public	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators

			utilities) and have their data openly available to the public. Open data refers to data that is freely accessible, machine-readable, and usable by anyone, often related to business operations, performance, service quality, or other community-related activities.	
Level of intersectionality in rural governance practices.	Percentage of Government Decisions or Policies Influenced by Data-Driven Processes	(%)	This metric captures the degree to which government decisions—particularly at local levels—are informed by systematic data analysis, reflecting the adoption of data-driven governance practices. It measures the proportion of decisions or policies made by the government that leverage data analysis or data-driven insights.	
Level of intersectionality in rural governance practices.	Number of sectors/agencies involved in the digital policy-making process (Number)	(Number)	This metric captures the diversity of sectors (e.g., agriculture, health, education, tourism) contributing to digital policy formation. A higher number of sectors involved signals a cross-sectoral approach, helping to create digital policies that address varied needs within the rural community and encourage sectoral collaboration.	
Level of Investment for smart transition	Percentage of Public Spending and Budget Allocation for the SMART Transition in Rural Communities (%)	(%)	This metric reflects the portion of a community's total public spending directed toward projects and programs that enhance digital infrastructure, energy efficiency, smart mobility,	
Level of Investment for smart transition	Percentage of digital infrastructure or service projects co-funded by	(%)	This metric assesses the proportion of digital infrastructure and service projects that	

	private entities or partnerships (%)		receive financial backing from private entities, demonstrating the level of private sector investment in rural digital development. A higher percentage indicates a supportive investment environment, leveraging public-private partnerships (PPPs) to overcome funding constraints in rural areas.	
Level of Online Service Accessibility	Percentage of Villages Services Accessible Online (%)	(%)	This metric assesses the digital accessibility of municipal services by evaluating the share of services available through online platforms. The indicator calculates the proportion of all municipal services (such as permits, tax payments, and information requests) that are available for access or processing through online portals or digital platforms.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators; ITU 4903
Level of Online Service Accessibility	Percentage of Village Services Integrated with Regional/National Digital Platforms (%)	(%)	The metric represents the proportion of village services accessible through or interconnected with larger digital networks. It captures the share of local services (such as public administration, healthcare, emergency response, and tourism) that are digitally connected to regional or national platforms, enabling centralized access, interoperability, and streamlined service delivery.	
Level of Online Service Accessibility	Percentage of Village Governmental Institutions with a Geographic Information System (GIS) operative units	(%)	This metric measures the percentage of governmental institutions in villages that have established a dedicated Geographic Information System (GIS) department or unit responsible for	

			managing spatial data and analysis.	
	Proportion of e-service companies with core business related to GIS serving the public, companies, government and other organizations.	% of companies		ITU 4901

Services of General Interest: Indicators and metrics

Indicator list

Table 21. Service of General Interest - Indicators and their prioritization

Dimensions	Sub-dimensions	Indicators	Definitions	Total score	Veto Factor
Services of General Interest	Healthcare	Level of Digitalization of Healthcare Systems	Assesses the extent to which digital technologies are integrated into healthcare systems in rural communities to improve access, efficiency, and quality of care.		
	Education	Level of Digitalization in Rural Schools	Evaluates the integration and usage of digital technologies in rural educational institutions to enhance learning outcomes and accessibility.		
	General Services	Level of Digital Accessibility in Services of General Interest	Measures the availability and ease of use of digital tools for accessing general public services in rural areas, such as administrative processes and utilities.		

Self-assessment

Before proceeding with the ranking process, participants are encouraged to carefully consider the following questions:

- What is the relative significance of each indicator in achieving the objectives of the selected project?
- How does each specific indicator contribute to the success and long-term sustainability of the project?

Rank each pair of indicators in the pairwise matrix below based on preference, using the scoring system provided. The scale ranges from 1 to 3:

- “One” indicates that the two indicators are equally important;
- “Two” indicates that one indicator is moderately more important than the other;
- “Three” indicates that one indicator is significantly more important than the other.

For each pair of indicators choose a value from 1 to 3. A 3 or 2 to the left column chart shows that the statement on the left is significantly or moderately more important than the one on the right, while a 2 or 3 to the right column chart indicates that the statement on the right is moderately or significantly more important than the one on the left.

Table 22. Service of General Interest - pairwise matrix

	3	2	1	2	3	
Level of Digitalization of Healthcare Systems						Level of Digitalization in Rural Schools
Level of Digitalization of Healthcare Systems						Level of Digital Accessibility in Services of General Interest
Level of Digitalization in Rural Schools						Level of Digital Accessibility in Services of General Interest

Completing all pairwise comparisons, participants calculate the **total score** for each indicator using “points” across the rows. The values should be added with a positive or negative sign based on the indicator's position in the matrix.

After finalizing the ranking of indicators, reflect on the **essential indicators** that directly impact the project's core objectives and feasibility.

- Any indicator that directly influences the project's success or its ability to meet legal, technical, or environmental requirements should be considered as a **Veto Factor**.
- If any indicator is flagged as a Veto Factor, it must be treated with utmost importance in the decision-making process, even if its ranking in the pairwise comparison is lower than others.
- When completing the ranking and prioritization of indicators, stakeholders should ensure that the Veto Factor is integrated into the final decision.

Metrics, units, importance and sources

Table 23. Service of General Interest - Metrics and their units

Status indicators	Metric	Units	Importance/Definition	Sources
Level of digitalization of healthcare system	Percentage of healthcare structures offering telehealth services	(%)	By tracking the percentage of healthcare structures offering telehealth, we can assess how accessible essential medical services are for rural residents, even in remote locations. This metric also helps gauge efforts to provide equitable healthcare solutions for rural populations and measure progress in providing healthcare solutions that make more efficient use of limited resources.	(Mohammadzadeh et al., 2023)
Level of digitalization of healthcare system	Number of IoT Mobile Remote Devices for Health Monitoring available per 100.000 population	(%)	This metric measures the proportion of devices in rural areas that utilize the Internet of Things (IoT) for health monitoring purposes normalized per 100.000 population. These devices can include wearable technology (e.g., smartwatches, fitness trackers, sensors) and other health-related IoT devices that track various health metrics such as heart rate, physical activity, and other vital signs.	(Mohammadzadeh et al., 2023)
Digital Literacy Initiatives	Ratio of Digital Literacy Initiatives with Partnerships Between Schools and Research Institutions/Tech Companies to Other Educations (Ratio)	(Ratio)	This metric measures the ratio of digital literacy initiatives that involve partnerships between schools and research institutions or tech companies to the total number of educational initiatives	

			implemented in rural communities. A higher ratio suggests that schools are prioritizing innovative and resource-rich programs that can provide students with essential digital skills	
Level of Digital Accessibility in Services of general interest	Percentage of rural post offices offering digital services, such as online parcel tracking or digital payments (%)		This metric measures the proportion of rural post offices that provide digital services, such as online parcel tracking, digital payments, and other electronic services. As rural areas often face challenges related to service accessibility, this indicator highlights the efforts of post offices (always physically in the area) to modernize and improve service delivery through digital means.	
Level of Digital Accessibility in Services of general interest	Number of digital kiosks or access points for public services in rural areas per 100.000 population	(Number)	This metric quantifies the number of digital kiosks or access points available for public services in rural areas, normalized per 100.000 residents. These kiosks may provide access to government services, information, and online resources.	
Level of Digital Accessibility in Services of general interest	Percentage of public services that can be booked online	(%)	This metric measures the percentage of public services (such as healthcare appointments, booking of public swimming pools, library reservations, and other municipal services) that offer online booking options. It reflects the level of digital accessibility and convenience provided	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators

			by public institutions to the community.	
Level of Digital Accessibility in Services of general interest	Percentage of public library technology programs designed for senior citizens	(%)	This metric measures the proportion of technology programs offered by public libraries that are specifically designed for senior citizens. These programs may include digital literacy workshops, computer training, internet safety sessions, and access to technology resources tailored to the needs of older adults.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Level of Digital Accessibility in Services of general interest	Percentage of Rural Banks Offering Digital Banking Services	(%)	This metric measures the proportion of banks in rural areas that provide digital banking services, including mobile banking, online account management, and electronic fund transfers.	
Level of Digital Accessibility in Services of general interest	Monthly number of visits to online databases offered by public libraries per 100.000 population	(Total population/Total number of visits) ×100.000	The Public Library Online Visit metric measures the monthly number of visits to the online databases provided by public libraries, normalized per 100.000 people in the villages population. This metric highlights the level of usage of digital library resources by the community and provides insights into how well public libraries are adapting to the growing demand for digital access to information.	DigComp Framework; ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Level of Digitalization in Rural Schools	Percentage of Schools in Rural Areas with High-Speed Internet Connectivity	(%)	This metric measures the proportion of schools in rural areas equipped with high-speed internet access, defined as a connection	

			sufficient to support modern educational tools, online resources, video conferencing, and digital learning platforms. High-speed internet is generally classified as a minimum download speed of 25 Mbps and upload speed of 3 Mbps, although definitions may vary by region.	
Level of Digitalization in Rural Schools	Number of students per school digital learning devices (laptop, computers, tablets)	(Student/Devices)	The Digital Learning Devices metric measures the ratio of students to digital learning devices, such as laptops, computers, and tablets, available in a school. This metric helps assess the availability of technology for educational purposes and the level of access students have to these critical tools for learning.	DigComp Framework; ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators for smart cities; (OECD, 2022)
Level of Digitalization in Rural Schools	Percentage of teachers who received formal training in using ICT for teaching, primary and secondary education	(%)	This metric measures the percentage of teachers in primary education in a given areas who have received formal training in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) for the purpose of enhancing their teaching practices. This metric tracks the extent to which teachers are equipped with the skills to integrate ICT into their teaching methods, reflecting the overall readiness of educators to work with digital tools in classrooms.	DigComp Framework; (OECD, 2022)
Level of Digitalization in Rural Schools	Average number of digital skills training	(Number)	This metric measures the availability and	DigComp Framework; (OECD, 2022)

	programs offered per school within a rural area,		accessibility of digital skills training programs offered directly within rural schools, reflecting the degree to which these programs are accessible to students regardless of school location or geographic area size. By focusing on each school individually, this metric provides a more accurate picture of digital skills support within the rural education system.	
Level of Digitalization in Rural Schools	Ratio of Educational Programs to Online Programs	(Ratio)	This metric calculates the proportion of all educational programs that are conducted online. It reflects the extent to which educational offerings in rural areas are accessible digitally. The ratio provides a clearer sense of how much of the educational programming is moving online relative to the overall programming in rural areas	
Level of Digitalization in Rural Schools	Percentage of Rural Schools Offering Hybrid (Online and In-Person) Classes	(%)	This metric measures the percentage of rural schools that provide hybrid learning options, combining both online and in-person instruction. Hybrid learning allows students the flexibility to attend classes in multiple formats, supporting accessibility for rural populations with logistical or connectivity constraints.	
Level of Digitalization in Rural Schools	Percentage of Schools Implementing	(%)	This metric measures the percentage of schools using	

	Electronic Registers for students		electronic registers to record, monitor, and manage student attendance, academic performance, and other essential information. Electronic registers replace traditional paper records, enabling schools to streamline data management and improve accuracy.	
Level of Digitalization in Rural Schools	Percentage of classes with interactive whiteboard (IWB)	(%)	This metric measures the percentage of total classes equipped with interactive whiteboards (IWBs). IWBs are digital displays that allow teachers and students to interact with content, enhancing engagement and enabling a more dynamic, multimedia-driven approach to learning. IWBs are valuable for rural schools, where access to diverse educational resources may be limited.	
Level of digitalization of healthcare system	Number of persons with special needs that have real-time ICT-based interactive mapping applications per 100 000 population	Number	?	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Level of digitalization of healthcare system	Percentage of Village Citizens with an Updated Electronic Health Record (EHR)	(%)	The Electronic Health Record (EHR) is the tool through which citizens can trace and consult the entire history of their health care life, sharing it with healthcare professionals to ensure a more effective and efficient service.	(Mohammadzadeh et al., 2023)

Level of digitalization of healthcare system	Percentage of the city's population with online unified health file accessible to health care providers (%)	(%)	The indicators quantify the extent to which rural citizens maintain and update their health records, enabling secure and efficient sharing of medical histories with healthcare providers. This indicator highlights how well-equipped a rural health system is in leveraging digital health data to support accessible, continuous, and coordinated healthcare across the community.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
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Environment and Climate-Related SDGs: Indicators and metrics

Indicator list

Table 24. Environment and Climate-Related SDGs - Indicators and their prioritization

Dimensions	Sub-dimensions	Indicators	Definitions	Total score	Veto Factor
Environment and Environmental and Climate-Related SDGs	Protection, Conservation, and Enhancement of Natural Capital	Degree of Digitalization in Monitoring Systems	Evaluates the integration of digital technologies in monitoring environmental systems, such as ecosystems, water, air quality, noise, waste, and wastewater, to enhance data collection, analysis, and management.		
	Mitigation of Environmental Pressures and Risks	Degree of Integrated Water Resource Management Implementation	Measures the extent to which integrated approaches to water management, incorporating digital tools, are implemented to optimize usage, reduce risks, and preserve resources.		
		Level of Risk Reduction Systems Implemented	Evaluates the deployment of systems to mitigate environmental risks (e.g., flooding, drought, pollution) using digital and smart technologies.		
	Development of a Resource-Efficient, Low-Carbon Economy	Status of Smart Waste and Recycling Management	Assesses the deployment of smart technologies to optimize waste collection, sorting, and recycling, promoting resource efficiency and reducing		

			environmental impact.		
		Status of Smart Water Resource Management	Measures the implementation of digital technologies in water resource management to enhance efficiency, reduce losses, and support conservation.		

Self-assessment

Before proceeding with the ranking process, participants are encouraged to carefully consider the following questions:

- What is the relative significance of each indicator in achieving the objectives of the selected project?
- How does each specific indicator contribute to the success and long-term sustainability of the project?

Rank each pair of indicators in the pairwise matrix below based on preference, using the scoring system provided. The scale ranges from 1 to 3:

- “One” indicates that the two indicators are equally important;
- “Two” indicates that one indicator is moderately more important than the other;
- “Three” indicates that one indicator is significantly more important than the other.

For each pair of indicators choose a value from 1 to 3. A 3 or 2 to the left column chart shows that the statement on the left is significantly or moderately more important than the one on the right, while a 2 or 3 to the right column chart indicates that the statement on the right is moderately or significantly more important than the one on the left.

Table 25. Environment and Climate-Related SDGs - pairwise matrix

	3	2	1	2	3	
Degree of Digitalization in Monitoring Systems						Degree of Integrated Water Resource Management Implementation
Degree of Digitalization in						Level of Risk Reduction Systems

Monitoring Systems						Implemented
Degree of Digitalization in Monitoring Systems						Status of Smart Waste and Recycling Management
Degree of Digitalization in Monitoring Systems						Status of Smart Water Resource Management
Degree of Integrated Water Resource Management Implementation						Level of Risk Reduction Systems Implemented
Degree of Integrated Water Resource Management Implementation						Status of Smart Waste and Recycling Management
Degree of Integrated Water Resource Management Implementation						Status of Smart Water Resource Management
Level of Risk Reduction Systems Implemented						Status of Smart Waste and Recycling Management
Level of Risk Reduction Systems Implemented						Status of Smart Water Resource Management
Status of Smart Waste and Recycling Management						Status of Smart Water Resource Management

Completing all pairwise comparisons, participants calculate the **total score** for each indicator using “points” across the rows. The values should be added with a positive or negative sign based on the indicator’s position in the matrix.

After finalizing the ranking of indicators, reflect on the **essential indicators** that directly impact the project's core objectives and feasibility.

- Any indicator that directly influences the project's success or its ability to meet legal, technical, or environmental requirements should be considered as a **Veto Factor**.
- If any indicator is flagged as a Veto Factor, it must be treated with utmost importance in the decision-making process, even if its ranking in the pairwise comparison is lower than others.
- When completing the ranking and prioritization of indicators, stakeholders should ensure that the Veto Factor is integrated into the final decision.

Metrics, units, importance and sources

Table 26. Environment and Climate-Related SDGs - Metrics and their units

Status indicators	Metric	Units	Importance/Definition	Sources
Degree of digitalizations of monitoring systems (ecosystems)	Percentage of Rural Ecosystems Mapped by Remote Sensing Monitoring	(%)	The percentage of rural ecosystems mapped by remote sensing and the frequency of the mapping reflect a community's capacity to monitor environmental changes, adapt to ecological challenges, and prevent adverse impacts on natural resources. Remote sensing refers to the process of detecting and tracking the physical characteristics of rural landscapes by measuring reflected and emitted radiation from a distance. This is achieved using remote sensors, which can be satellite-based or mounted on aircraft.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Degree of digitalizations of monitoring systems (Air)	Number of outdoor installations of ICT based air quality monitoring systems per km ²	(Number)	ICT based systems refer to air quality monitoring systems with sensors, which transmit measurements to a database where daily alerts and information are available and yearly summaries for each	ITU 4903

			monitoring stations are computed.	
Degree of digitalizations of monitoring systems (Air)	Application of ICT based monitoring system for particles and toxic substances	(%)	Proportion of rural area covered by outdoor ICT based monitoring system for particles and toxic substances. This indicator captures to what extent ICT monitors the air pollution (PM10, PM2.5, toxic substances etc.). %	ITU 4901
Degree of digitalizations of monitoring systems (ecosystems)	Annual frequency of ecosystem remote sensing monitoring	(Ratio)	In rural contexts, this metric helps local authorities and communities manage natural resources, detect environmental changes, and support conservation efforts.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Degree of digitalizations of monitoring systems (Nois)	Proportion of the rural area with applied ICT based noise monitoring.	(%)	Proportion of the rural area with applied ICT based noise monitoring. This indicator measures how ICT is used to monitor how the inhabitants are exposed to acoustical noise within rural areas, especially focusing on noise sensitive areas.	ITU 4901
Degree of digitalizations of monitoring systems (Waste)	Percentage of the villages population that has a door-to-door garbage collection with an individual telemetering of household waste quantities (%)	(%)	In rural areas, where waste collection routes may be longer and less frequent, telemetering enhances efficiency by allowing for collections based on actual need.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Degree of digitalizations of monitoring systems (Wastewater)	Percentage of the wastewater pipeline network monitored by a real-time data tracking sensor system	(%)	This metric measures the proportion of the wastewater pipeline network within a given area equipped with real-time tracking sensors. These systems continuously monitor key parameters like flow rates, pressure, and potential contaminants, enabling rapid response to issues such as leaks, blockages, or contamination.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators

Degree of digitalizations of monitoring systems (water)	Number of real-time ICT-based environmental water quality monitoring stations per 100.000 population	(Number)	A remotely operated, real-time ICT-based system can help to monitor climate change impacts on environment (e.g., air and water quality). Such systems can also provide real-time observations, data processing, and analysis, giving people timely information on the safety of a city's environmental quality.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Degree of digitalizations of monitoring systems (Water)	Density of Outdoor ICT-Based Water Quality Monitoring Systems per Surface Water Area (Number per km ²)	(Number)	This metric measures the number of outdoor installations of ICT-based water quality monitoring systems deployed per square kilometer of surface water, including lakes, rivers, wetlands, and estuaries. These systems provide real-time data on water quality, helping track key environmental metrics such as pH levels, dissolved oxygen, turbidity, and contaminant presence.	
Degree of digitalizations of monitoring systems (Water)	Percentage of drinking water under water quality monitoring by a real-time water quality monitoring station	(%)	This metric represents the proportion of the drinking water supply monitored continuously by real-time water quality monitoring stations. These stations track critical parameters, such as pH, turbidity, contaminant levels, and chemical composition, to ensure water safety and compliance with health standards.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Degree of digitalizations of monitoring systems (Weather)	Number of Public Weather Stations per Square Kilometer	(number/km ²)	This metric measures the density of public weather monitoring stations, which is crucial for tracking local climate conditions, predicting extreme weather events, and providing accurate forecasts.	

Degree of digitalizations of monitoring systems	Proportion of the sewage system monitored using ICT NOTE – Monitoring includes both inspection and controlling.	% of the sewage system	This metric measures the percentage of a rural area's sewage infrastructure that is actively monitored through Information and Communication Technologies (ICT). In rural communities, sewage systems often cover large areas with limited resources available for maintenance and repair. Monitoring through ICT is essential for efficient and proactive management, helping to identify issues before they escalate into costly repairs or environmental hazards.	(ITU 4901)
Degree of digitalizations of monitoring systems (Air)	Number of real-time ICT-based air quality monitoring stations per 100.000 population	(Number)	A remotely operated, real-time ICT-based system can help to monitor climate change impacts on environment (e.g., air and water quality). Such systems can also provide real-time observations, data processing, and analysis, giving people timely information on the safety of a city's environmental quality.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Degree of digitalizations of monitoring systems (Nois)	Number of outdoor installations with applied ICT based noise monitoring per km ²	(Number)	ICT based systems refer to noise monitoring systems with sensors, which transmit measurements to a database where daily alerts and information are available and yearly summaries for each monitoring station are computed.	ITU 4903
Degree of digitalizations of monitoring systems (Waste)	Percentage of Waste Drop-Off Centers (Containers) Equipped with Telemetering	(%)	This metric measures the proportion of waste collection points, containers, or drop-off centers that are equipped with telemetering systems. Telemetering technology	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators

			enables real-time monitoring of container fill levels, optimizing waste collection schedules and reducing unnecessary trips.	
Degree of integrated water resources management implementation	% of the drainage system Proportion of the drainage systems monitored in real-time using ICT.	Calculate as: Numerator: The sum of the total drainage areas that are covered by the monitoring nodes. Denominator: The total drainage area of the river basin closed to the outlet (lake or ocean).	Monitoring includes both inspection and controlling. Water quantity observation stations are used as a reference for evaluating an index representing the density of the natural and artificial drainage system monitoring network. Each observation node is associated with a drainage area either for natural drainage (rivers, lakes) or for artificial systems (sewers, urban storm drains, etc.)	ITU 4901, ITU 4903
Level of risk reduction systems implemented	Percentage of population reached by early warning and evacuation systems measure / news on portable devices	(%)	This metric measures the proportion of a rural area's population that receives early warning alerts and evacuation instructions via portable devices, such as mobile phones or tablets. These alerts are typically part of emergency systems designed to inform residents about imminent natural disasters or other safety threats. Reaching residents through portable devices ensures that even in dispersed communities, people are aware of impending threats and know how to respond swiftly.	
Level of risk reduction systems implemented	Presence of GIS app to risk reduction and preventions (for instance to detect and map forest fires, foods impact, toxic cloud etc, and improve response and public safety)	(%)	This metric assesses whether a Geographic Information System (GIS) application is available and utilized within a rural area to support risk reduction and prevention efforts. Such GIS applications enable the detection, mapping, and real-time	

			monitoring of hazards, including forest fires, flood impacts, toxic clouds, and other environmental risks. By providing visual, location-based data, GIS applications allow for more informed decision-making, improving response times and enhancing public safety protocols.	
Smart Waste and Recycling Management	Percentage of the villages' electronic waste that is recycled (%)	(%)	The proportion of electronic waste generated in the village that is processed and recycled rather than disposed of in landfills. E-waste recycling reduces environmental pollution and allows for resource recovery, minimizing the negative impacts on rural landscapes and ecosystems.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Smart Waste and Recycling Management	Percentage of waste drop-off centres (containers) equipped with telemetering (%)	(%)	Measures the share of waste drop-off centers or containers that use telemetering technology, enabling remote monitoring of container fill levels and optimized waste collection. Telemetering in waste management reduces unnecessary collection trips, lowering operational costs and carbon emissions, contributing to a more efficient waste management system.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Smart Waste and Recycling Management	Percentage of treated wastewater being reused (%)	(%)	The proportion of treated wastewater that is repurposed for activities like irrigation, industrial processes, or other non-potable uses. Using treated wastewater helps conserve freshwater resources, supports agricultural activities in water-scarce areas, and is an essential practice for sustainable water management.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators

Status of the Smart Water Resource Management	Percentage of the community's water distribution network monitored by a smart water system (%)	(%)	This metric measures the proportion of the community's water distribution network that is monitored via a smart water system, which may include sensors, leak detection, and remote control capabilities. Smart monitoring allows for proactive maintenance and reduces water loss, crucial for sustainability and resource efficiency in rural areas.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Status of the Smart Water Resource Management	Percentage of households with smart water meters (%)	(%)	The percentage of households in the community that have smart water meters installed, providing real-time data on water usage. Smart meters enable households to monitor and reduce their water consumption, promoting water conservation and helping manage resources effectively in rural areas.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators
Status of the Smart Water Resource Management	Percentage of buildings in the community with smart water meters (%)	(%)	Measures the percentage of buildings (residential, commercial, or public) equipped with smart water meters for monitoring and managing water consumption. Equipping buildings with smart meters provides data for more effective water use planning, which supports community-wide resource efficiency and reduces waste.	ISO 37122:2019 - Indicators

